

Strategies to Obtain Working Capital for Small Businesses

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ABSTRACT

The inability to obtain working capital can affect small business continuity, especially in the long term. Small business owners must be able to access working capital or else risk business survival through liquidity shortages, lost customers, and falling profitability. Grounded in the pecking order theory, the purpose of this qualitative multiple-case study was to explore the strategies employed by small business owners to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond five years. The participants were eight small business owners in Maryland who had successful strategies to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond five years. Data were collected through semistructured one-on-one interviews and publicly available documents. Thematic analysis was conducted following Yin's five-phase process—compiling, disassembling, reassembling, interpreting, and concluding—to analyze the data. Five key themes emerged: (a) financing through retained earnings, (b) financing through nontraditional lending sources, (c) limited access to external funding in the early years, (d) reliance on external financing during later and critical business stages, and (e) minimizing operational costs and expenses. A key recommendation is that entrepreneurs use internal financing to sustain operations, minimizing the need for external funds. The implication for positive social change includes the potential for small business owners to sustain operations for more than five years, thereby providing jobs and generating tax revenue for citizens and communities.

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KEYWORDS: Working capital, Small business continuity, Pecking order theory, Retained earnings, Nontraditional lending, External financing

SECTION 1: FOUNDATION OF THE STUDY

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are critical to the economies of the United States and the world. The U.S. Small Business Administration (U.S. SBA) Office of Advocacy (2020) found that SME owners employed more than 60.6 million individuals, constituting 47.1% of the private workforce in 2017. SME leaders contribute to international trade by positively influencing exports. In 2018, 97.5% of total U.S. exports were from SMEs, generating 32.0% of earnings from exports (United States Census Bureau, 2021). Globally, SMEs are crucial in developed and developing economies. The World Bank (2022b) reported that 90% of businesses are SMEs, comprising more than 50% of jobs worldwide. Despite their contributions to the economy, SME leaders face challenges in accessing financing, which is the primary constraint to growth. The COVID-19 pandemic led to more significant challenges in accessing capital due to national and international economic difficulties (Shafi et al., 2020), as the inability to access funding increased the risk of insolvency

and the loss of competitive advantages (Kalemli-Ozcan et al., 2020). To address SME leaders' challenges in accessing capital, scholars and policymakers must understand the strategies that facilitate fund acquisition. This qualitative descriptive multiple case study further explains how SMEs can access funding by exploring the strategies SMEs use to acquire working capital.

Background of the Problem

SME owners play a critical role in Maryland's economy by creating employment, promoting innovation, and expanding the tax base. In 2016, more than 1.2 million people worked for Maryland SMEs, comprising 49.5% of the private workforce (U.S. SBA Office of Advocacy, 2020). The problem is the high number of SMEs ceasing operations in the United States. According to the U.S. SBA Office of Advocacy (2020), 3,911 SMEs exited Maryland's market in 2018, resulting in 14,033 lost jobs. External funding is necessary for the sustainability and growth of small businesses (Neagu, 2016). Access to financial resources is essential for business leaders to pay for operating expenses,

debt, inventory, and business growth. Many business leaders attribute business failures to external factors, although internal management capabilities and approaches significantly impact business sustainability (Eggers & Lin, 2015). Poor management skills, financial literacy, and an inability to access finances are the main reasons for business failure (Lee, 2016). I explored Maryland small business owners' effective strategies to obtain working capital for business continuity for 5 years or longer.

Problem and Purpose

Small business owners encounter challenges obtaining working capital (U.S. Federal Reserve Bank, 2017). Insufficient access to funds, including lines of credit, leads to the failure of 29% of small businesses within the first 5 years of operation (Shabat, 2019). The general business problem is that some small business owners cannot access capital, threatening business survival through liquidity shortages, lost customers, and falling profitability. The specific business problem is that some small business owners lack strategies to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond 5 years.

The purpose of this qualitative descriptive multiple case study was to explore strategies that small business owners used to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond 5 years. The target population was small business owners in Maryland. The sample was eight small business owners in Maryland who had successfully obtained capital for business continuity and had been in business for at least 5 years. One implication for social change is that small business owners may be able to sustain operations, thus providing employment opportunities that could increase the standard of living and contribute to citizens' well-being in the local communities. Another implication for social change is that sustaining small business operations will allow customers to continue receiving the products and services they need, contributing to their quality of life and the sustainability of their household or business operations.

Population and Sampling

The population of the study was business owners of small manufacturing and wholesale businesses in Maryland with 500 or fewer employees. The sample comprised eight small business owners in Maryland who obtained working capital for business continuity. Recruitment occurred via purposive sampling to explore the strategies used by small business owners to obtain working capital within a changing business environment. The participant eligibility criteria were as follows: (a) owned a small manufacturing and wholesale business in Maryland, (b) employed 500 or fewer people, and (c) used successful strategies to obtain working capital for business continuity. One-on-one semistructured interviews and documents were the data sources for the study.

Nature of the Study

The three research methods are qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods (Yin, 2017). In a qualitative study, a researcher explores a phenomenon (Glaser & Strauss, 2017); in comparison, a quantitative scholar statistically measures the relationship between variables (Goertzen, 2017). A researcher employs qualitative and quantitative approaches in mixed methods (Yin, 2017). Because I did not use statistical measures to test a hypothesis and determine the relationship between variables to understand the research phenomenon in this study, neither the quantitative nor mixed methods approach was appropriate. I used the qualitative methodology with a descriptive multiple-case study design to explore a real-life phenomenon.

I considered narrative, ethnographic, phenomenological, and case study designs for this study. Using a narrative design, a researcher obtains individuals' life stories in a storytelling format (Marshall & Rossman, 2016). The ethnographic design is appropriate for the cultural study of specific groups. In a phenomenological study, participants describe their lived experiences of a phenomenon (Hanson et al., 2011). A case study is appropriate to capture a real-life phenomenon in a specific setting by asking *how* and *why* questions (Cronin, 2014). This type of qualitative design was ideal for the current study because I explored a research phenomenon in a real-life setting by asking *how* and *what* questions to identify common factors.

Research Question

What strategies do small business owners use to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond 5 years?

Interview Questions

1. What strategies did you use to obtain working capital?
2. What are potential sources of working capital?
3. What are the significant challenges you encountered in securing working capital?
4. How did you overcome the challenges you encountered in securing working capital?
5. What strategies did you use to develop successful banking relationships and secure working capital?
6. Based on your experience, how have external funding or new equity affected your business sustainability and profitability?
7. What else can you share about the funding strategies you used to sustain your business during the first 5 years of your operation?

Theoretical Framework

This study's theoretical framework was the pecking order theory introduced by Myers and Majluf (1984) based

on seminal work by Donaldson (1961). According to the pecking order theory, business owners use a hierarchy of financing sources—retained earnings, debt, and new equity—only moving to the next when the previous option is unavailable. Business leaders prefer to use retained earnings for financing due to the lack of risk and associated costs (Myers & Majluf, 1984). The pecking order theory was an appropriate framework to explore strategies that small business owners used to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond 5 years based on the three financial areas of interest: internal funding, debt issuance, and equity.

Operational Definitions

Adaptive leadership: A style of leadership that involves understanding the leadership process, strategizing, and adapting to change across all organizational levels (Reiman et al., 2015).

Informal turnaround: A commercial lender’s informal notice of rejection should an SME owner apply for a loan (Rostamkalaei et al., 2018).

Information asymmetry: Information asymmetry occurs when stakeholders have inequality or unequal information access (Mhlanga, 2021).

Sustainable growth rate: The maximum rate of growth an organization can maintain without acquiring additional funds (Inc., n.d.).

Assumptions, Limitations, and Delimitations

Assumptions

Assumptions are beliefs that a researcher cannot verify but are presumed to be true (Marshall & Rossman, 2016). In this study, the first assumption was that a qualitative approach with a descriptive multiple-case study design was appropriate for answering the research question. Another assumption was that the participants would answer the interview questions honestly. If participants withheld information or misrepresented their experiences, my findings might not be accurate. I also assumed that interviews with eight small business owners and reviews of their company documents would be sufficient to achieve data saturation, without which I could not have confidence in my results.

Limitations

Limitations stem from methodology and design issues beyond the researcher’s control (Yin, 2017). A limitation of this study was the use of qualitative methodology because qualitative findings are subjective and dependent upon the researcher’s interpretation (see Dennis, 2018). Qualitative findings are specific to the population studied and not transferable to other populations, settings, or phenomena (Rahman, 2020; Simon & Goes, 2013). Qualitative data analysis was a limitation because reliability and validity depend on the researcher’s determination of relevant themes and data saturation (Simon & Goes, 2013). Another limitation was the time-intensive data analysis in case studies (see Heale & Twycross, 2018; Rahman, 2020),

particularly those with participant interviews (see Queirós et al., 2017). Participants’ honesty and willingness to share information and documents could have been a limitation. In one-on-one interviews, social desirability bias may result when participants provide answers to present themselves in the best light rather than answering truthfully (Bergen & Labonté, 2020).

Delimitations

Delimitations are the boundaries a researcher sets for the study (Theofanidis & Fountouki, 2019). I limited the scope of the present study to explore the phenomenon of strategies small business owners have used to secure working capital for business continuity. Delimitations for participation included owners of manufacturing and wholesale small businesses in Maryland with 500 or fewer employees.

Significance of the Study

Some small businesses fail because of insufficient access to working capital (Liu, 2015). Securing working capital could ensure business continuity and growth, resulting in ongoing advancement opportunities for employees and a thriving community. The findings of this study may be of value to businesses. Small business owners could learn the strategies other small business owners used to obtain working capital successfully, thus ensuring business continuity beyond 5 years. Contributions to positive social change may come from more small business owners maintaining their businesses’ operations, continuing to employ their workers, and economically benefiting the community.

Contribution to Business Practice

The findings of this study could contribute to business practice in at least two ways. Small business owners may learn about and implement credit acquisition strategies that lead to increased business performance in the long term. Individuals considering opening small businesses may find this study helpful when creating their business plans and forecasts. The research findings may be valuable to small business owners, banking officials, government agencies, and creditors in understanding small business leaders’ strategies to access credit.

Implications for Positive Social Change

Small business owners facilitate the local economy’s health (J. M. Brown, 2018). The community could benefit from the results of this study in many ways. Considering that sustainability is a pathway to a significant competitive advantage, small business owners may be willing to participate in new programs in the community and invest more in their workforce’s well-being. More small businesses operating in the community means job creation, poverty reduction, and the potential for a higher standard of living among citizens (Shibia & Barako, 2017). Employees’ families also benefit when individuals prosper in a healthy

working environment with increased opportunities for employment.

A Review of the Professional and Academic Literature

The literature review on the research topic involved accessing journals and seminal books through the Walden University Library website. Databases searched included ABI/INFORM Complete, ProQuest Central, Emerald Management, Business Source Complete, Academic Research Complete, and SAGE Premier. I also performed searches through Google Scholar and AOSIS Open Journals. Google Scholar queries provided interdisciplinary results, including conference proceedings, and AOSIS Open Journals searches returned peer-reviewed scholarly articles from a wide range of academic disciplines. A review of business journals and publications returned research specific to small businesses and small business owners. Government websites, including those of the U.S. SBA and the Maryland Chamber of Commerce, provided valuable information on small businesses' credit strategies and programs.

In searching for relevant literature, I prioritized peer-reviewed articles published between 2018 and 2021 to obtain current information and findings. Ulrich's Periodicals Directory was a helpful tool to ensure the selection of peer-reviewed articles. Keywords and combinations of keywords used for the search were *small business*, *business lending*, *small business lending*, *small business financing*, *credit strategies*, *bank loans*, *sources of financing*, *working capital*, *small business and financial constraints*, *small business continuity*, *capital structure*, *information asymmetry*, and *the lending process*, *small businesses and audited financial statements*, *small business leadership*, *the theory of discouraged borrowers*, and *small business and discouraged borrower*. The literature search produced 160 resources, including 138 (86%) peer-reviewed articles published between 2018 and 2021.

I compared the work of different scholars to obtain varied perspectives on the research phenomenon. The first overarching concept, the likelihood of applying for and approving a bank loan for working capital, emerged from discussions of the pecking order theory in the context of small businesses. The discussion topics related to the second concept, small businesses, included other forms of working capital, small business sustainability, small business challenges, and government roles. Small business financing emerged from literature on funding programs, sources of capital, and credit strategies, with the fourth concept of information symmetry in the lending process.

This qualitative descriptive multiple case study explored strategies that small business owners use to obtain working capital for business continuity. The literature review begins with an in-depth exploration of the pecking order theory's conceptual framework and how researchers have used it in related studies. Other relevant topics discussed are small business financing, credit strategies,

information symmetry in lending, and audited financial statements.

Theoretical Framework

Pecking order is a theory of corporate finance that provides a model for the cost of financing as theoretically asymmetric (Myers & Majluf, 1984). Donaldson (1961) approached the concept of modeling financing via pecking order, and the theory gained popularity with Myers and Majluf (1984), who provided a meaningful understanding of potential financing sources. The model suggests that business owners acquire financing from three primary sources: retained earnings, debt, and new equity. For financial success, company leaders must consider how they source their funding, including the associated costs. Business owners use internal financing before acquiring debt, with equity as the last option when others have failed (Myers & Majluf, 1984). Although debt costs less than equity, equity repayment is unnecessary when earnings decline (Gurrea-Martínez & Remolina, 2019). Pecking order theory indicates that business owners turn to debt and equity only after exhausting retained earnings.

The preference to use retained earnings first has direct links to the associated costs of using those funds, with retained earnings the cheapest and preferred funding source, followed by debt, and finally equity, which is typically the most expensive form of funding (Myers & Majluf, 1984). According to the pecking order theory, information asymmetry impacts managerial action because a company's prospects improve, and risk diminishes as the decision-maker understands more about the company and the priority and cost of its funding needs. Information asymmetry influences how business owners rank the funding type they seek and obtain (Dhaene et al., 2017). Business owners generally use retained earnings until they are no longer available and then turn to debt issuance to meet company needs. Company leaders strongly prefer using retained earnings and less often subsidized loans, which are typically more expensive (Zeidan et al., 2018). When additional financing is not readily accessible, business owners might have to liquidate assets to obtain the capital needed to stay in business.

There is no risk of a loan default when using internally generated funds. Business leaders prefer debt to equity (Myers & Majluf, 1984), as equity could accompany greater risk, higher financing costs, and less company control. New equity financing providers primarily invest in the company's potential and, as part owners, have some control over its operation (Dowling et al., 2019). Business owners prefer not to cede equity, so they consider equity financing a last resort. Company leaders use this option to raise additional capital to sustain operations beyond 5 years. Pecking order theory includes this study's three financial areas of interest: internal funding, debt issuance, and equity.

Myers (1984) introduced the pecking order theory in a paper about stock issuance. The theory's constructs hold for other types of enterprise financing. Two of the four pecking order theory stages were relevant to this study. When business owners need funding, they favor internal financing over external financing. Should internal funding be unavailable, business leaders view debt over equity financing as the safest choice (Myers, 1984). Many researchers have examined the pecking order theory in real-world populations (most recently, Nguyen & Nguyen, 2020; Rao et al., 2019; Simatupang et al., 2019; Wijaya et al., 2020; Yıldırım & Çelik, 2021).

Firm and owner characteristics also contribute to the pecking order theory's applicability. Nguyen and Nguyen (2020) measured two criteria: firm performance and the ratio of liabilities to assets. The four firm-specific control variables were firm size, growth rate, liquidity, and fixed-to-total assets ratio. Nguyen and Nguyen reported three reasons company owners opt for internal financing: reduced dependence on other parties, greater financial autonomy, and firm confidentiality.

Researchers have identified the pecking order theory as the best approach to examine capital structure, and the owners of profitable companies with existing funds tended to use internal financing. Simatupang et al. (2019) conducted a causal-comparative study using panel data from 154 Indonesian nonfinancial companies with surplus funds. The researchers' findings supported the literature, with the owners of higher-profit companies more likely to use lower-risk internal financing. Yıldırım and Çelik (2021) reviewed 2000–2018 data from manufacturing companies on the Istanbul Stock Exchange to examine pecking order differences in small and large firms. In line with the pecking order theory, the researchers found the greatest support for the pecking order theory in small firms. Most business owners turned to debt financing after exhausting their internal resources (Yıldırım & Çelik, 2021).

The pecking order theory is particularly applicable to SMEs, as shown in studies of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs; Mittal & Raman, 2020; Rao et al., 2019). Mittal and Raman's (2020) exploration of MSME owners' financing preferences supported the pecking order theory. Of the three independent variables (owner gender, owner education, and type of ownership), two characteristics indicated a preference for external financing: owners with more education and enterprises run as companies. Rao et al. (2019) examined the balanced panel data of 174 nonfinancial-sector MSMEs in India to identify what factors contributed to the owners' financing choices. The results showed that owners of manufacturing MSMEs primarily used debt financing over retained earnings.

Criticisms of the Pecking Order Theory

Pecking order theory is a popular concept in capital structure literature and has received significant support and

criticism from researchers since its inception. Critics have argued that company leaders will follow a capital structure approach depending on the company's life cycle and prevailing economic conditions (Aghe Africa, 2017). Small business owners might not acquire external debt during startup or an economic recession. Business owners often engage in unrealistic and counterintuitive planning (Adomdza et al., 2016), which might lead to poor funding decisions and the need to raise funds from investors through additional debt or equity.

The primary factors impacting leverage ratio are the firm's size, tangibility, profitability, growth, liquidity, and operating leverage (Imtiaz et al., 2016). Profitability, liquidity, and operating leverage are negatively related to leverage and inversely associated with tangibility, growth, and size. As profitability, liquidity, and operating leverage increase, the need for external debt decreases, and vice versa. As tangibility, growth, and size increase, the need for leverage also grows. These relationships suggest that business owners' actions could be inconsistent with the pecking order theory (Imtiaz et al., 2016).

The pecking order theory is most applicable to mature, profitable companies and not small, new entities (Grigore & Gurău, 2019) due to the preference for using retained earnings before any other source of capital. Most owners of contemporary companies, especially small businesses, are unlikely to have generated retained earnings available for reinvestment. A lack of retained earnings means business owners must consider bank loans the first capital-raising option. Internal funding might also be inadequate to cover investment spending as there is a significant reliance on external financing.

Another criticism of the pecking order theory pertains to the confidence level of managers and small business owners. Overconfident managers prefer to address financing deficits with equity over debt or loans (Vivian & Xu, 2018). Overconfident managers might overvalue the use of equity over debt, underestimating the riskiness of future earnings. In small businesses and companies with high earnings volatility, managerial overconfidence significantly weakens applying the pecking order theory.

Contrasting Theories

The trade-off and market timing theories are similar to the pecking order theory but not chosen for this study.

Trade-Off Theory. Capital structure theories remain unclear in the literature. The pecking order (Myers & Majluf, 1984) and trade-off (Modigliani & Miller, 1958) theories provide a foundation for researching an optimum capital structure composition to increase a firm's value. Unlike the pecking order theory, which indicates a preferred order of capital acquisition, the trade-off theory suggests a target of optimum debt level for maximizing firm value. According to the pecking order theory, an optimal capital

structure is insufficient for increasing a firm’s market value. Until pecking order theory research began in 1999, scholars considered trade-off theory the best approach to explain capital structure (Simatupang et al., 2019).

Japanese firm leaders’ financing practices are consistent with the pecking order theory, with the deficit of available internal financing driving external debt financing (Jarallah et al., 2018). In Japan, business owners rely on internal financing, turning to external debt after exhausting internal resources and external equity when external debt is no longer available. The process is a financial necessity and not always a way to maximize firm value.

The trade-off theory suggests maximizing firm value using debt. Firm leaders face a debt target limiting the value of debt funding they can take on with decreased tax and capital costs (Simatupang et al., 2019). A business owner borrowing funds must make periodic interest payments, reducing free cash flow (Alipour et al., 2015).

According to the trade-off theory, debt acquisition depends on a firm’s resources. Business owners who develop their capital structure in alignment with the trade-off theory could obtain debt based on the size of their company assets (Horvatinović & Orsag, 2018). The owners of small businesses do not have the asset base to acquire debt easily. A direct relationship exists between the size of a company’s assets and the ability to acquire debt. Liquidity ratios could have a mixed effect on capital structure decisions (Alipour et al., 2015). Although trade-off theory is a common framework used to address SME financing, it was inappropriate for this study, given its focus on obtaining external resources to build leverage.

Market Timing Theory. Another alternative theory of capital structure is the market timing theory. According to this theory, business owners are more likely to issue equity to raise capital when the firm’s value is high and repurchase the equity when the value is low (Baker & Wurgler, 2002). Information asymmetry among small businesses creates market timing opportunities. Small business owners have limited access to the capital market, and raising external capital is an opportunity requiring strategic timing (Iyer & Javadi, 2018), decided by the management based on current market realities. Because market timing theory centers more around business owners basing their equity sales in times of market profitability, it was not appropriate for this study.

There is no risk associated with using retained earnings because, like profits, they are intended for reinvestment. Most business owners use retained earnings until they are no longer available and then turn to financing to meet company needs. Business owners prefer retaining profits to obtaining subsidized loans (Zeidan et al., 2018). When additional financing is not readily accessible, business owners might liquidate equity assets as a last resort to gain capital to stay in business.

Business owners prefer debt to equity (Myers & Majluf, 1984), which could be related to greater risk, higher financing costs, and less company control. Providers of new equity finance primarily invest in the company’s future potential and, as part owners, have some control over the company’s operation (Dowling et al., 2019). For these reasons, business owners may choose not to use additional equity and consider equity financing a last resort. Company leaders use equity financing to raise additional capital to sustain operations beyond the first 5 years.

Small Businesses

Small businesses, defined as commercial entities with fewer than 500 employees (U.S. SBA Office of Advocacy, 2020), play an essential role in economic growth through employment and trade (Ahmad et al., 2020; Malesios et al., 2021). In 2017, SMEs employed an estimated 60.6 million individuals in the United States, constituting 47.1% of private-sector workers. Small businesses have contributed to U.S. internal trade through exports. In 2018, small businesses were responsible for 97.5% of the firms’ exported goods, contributing to 32.0% of all earnings from exports. Small businesses positively affect the gross domestic product (Malesios et al., 2021; Woźniak et al., 2019).

Despite their economic contributions, SME owners continue to face challenges with access to financing, which is the primary constraint to their growth (World Bank, 2022b). To grow faster than their sustainable growth rate, company leaders must have access to capital to fund working capital, increase inventories and employees, and purchase property, plant, and equipment. Challenges in accessing funding increase the risk of insolvency and the loss of competitive advantages (Kalemlı-Ozcan et al., 2020). Compared to large organization leaders, small business owners are at a disadvantage in accessing finance due to limited credit history, incomplete record-keeping, insufficient collateral, and a lack of business planning expertise (R. Brown et al., 2022; Huang et al., 2020; Roy & Shaw, 2021). Inadequate working capital could contribute to the failure of small business start-ups, as owners require funds during the initial years of operation to pay creditors, taxes, wages, and overhead costs (Mazzarol & Reboud, 2020).

Small Business Sustainability

Sustainability concerns the environment, work requirements, human rights, business ethics, anticorruption, diversity, and gender equality (Tsvetkova et al., 2020). The concept of business sustainability has evolved to include attributes such as bio/green innovation and environmental issues (Burlea-Schiopoiu & Mihai, 2019). The issue of SME sustainability has gained traction since the 1970s in recognition of small businesses’ impacts on the environment and society (Sarango-Lalangui et al., 2018; Tsvetkova et al., 2020). Sustainability has become a goal ingrained in

businesses’ strategic missions and visions for corporate social responsibility. For small business owners, sustainability involves balancing the company’s interests (financial, material, and human resources) and the operating environment (social and economic environment; Burlea-Schiopoiu & Mihai, 2019).

Economic sustainability is also essential for small businesses. Like their medium-sized and larger counterparts, small businesses may significantly impact their immediate environments (Sarango-Lalangui et al., 2018). Economic sustainability allows small business owners to compete favorably and succeed in an otherwise challenging business environment (Tsvetkova et al., 2020). Sustainability enables small business owners to benefit from improved financing and access to labor and ideas (Long, 2020). Small business sustainability benefits local communities, resulting in improved infrastructure, better health, and increased access to employment. SME sustainability is crucial for the economy because of the businesses’ multifaceted role (Pu et al., 2021). The closure of SMEs could have profound impacts on the aggregate economy. As a result, there is a need to promote economic sustainability among SMEs (Pu et al., 2021).

Despite the importance of SMEs, small business owners lag behind medium and large business leaders in implementing economic and environmental sustainability initiatives. Poor financial resources and limited time prevent small business leaders from developing and implementing sustainability strategies (Burlea-Schiopoiu & Mihai, 2019). Often, small business owners perceive that incorporating environmental sustainability policies into their operations is risky without significant financial returns. The present study investigated how small business owners acquire working capital for business continuity. Small business owners should develop strategies to achieve and maintain economic sustainability, balancing the needs of their businesses and members of society. In this study, I explored the strategies small business owners used to obtain working capital for business continuity and sustainability using the framework of the pecking order theory.

Small Business Financing

Durst and Gerstlberger (2020) have studied SME financing, among other scholars. The leaders of national and international bodies, such as the United Nations, OECD, and the European Investment Bank, have implemented SME financing policies to encourage the growth of small and medium-sized businesses. Despite their organization’s role in the economy, SME business owners face challenges in accessing funding. Bartik et al. (2020) deemed SMEs financially fragile, with most lacking the financial strength to meet expenses.

Access to financing is a significant problem for small businesses (Mazzarol & Reboud, 2020). Small business owners receive funding from different sources,

including bootstrap financing. Bootstrap financing is a form of owner-provided financing from multiple sources—including savings, retained earnings from the business, and improved cash flow management and working capital techniques—to improve operational efficiency and profitability. Another source, equity financing, involves obtaining money from other investors by offering them a portion of ownership of the business. Small business leaders also obtain funds through debt financing, borrowing from lenders to invest in the business.

Small businesses contribute to Maryland’s economy by creating employment, promoting innovation, and expanding the tax base. According to the U.S. SBA Office of Advocacy (2020), small businesses employed more than 1.2 million people in Maryland in 2017. Small business insolvency in Maryland remains high, with more than 3,911 small businesses exiting in 2019 (U.S. SBA Office of Advocacy, 2020), resulting in 14,033 jobs lost. In response, government and private organization leaders have united to provide loans to small businesses in Maryland. The Small Business Development Financing Authority offers a range of funding programs to small businesses that do not meet the established requirements for commercial loans (Maryland Department of Commerce, 2021).

The Maryland Small Business COVID-19 RELIEF Grant Program helped during the 2020–2021 fiscal year when Maryland’s small businesses faced continued financial impacts from the pandemic. In 2020, state leaders established the program through bipartisan legislation, offering no- and low-cost 5-year term loans ranging from \$25,000 to \$200,000 (Maryland Department of Commerce, 2021). Grant funding allowed qualifying Maryland small business owners to obtain working capital and offset disrupted operations due to COVID-19.

Officials in some U.S. states, including Maryland, have implemented grants and programs for small business support and success. Access to financing remains challenging, and borrowers may become discouraged. This study’s participants discussed the financing options they explored and the strategies they used to obtain working capital.

Small Business Credit

Access to credit or other sources of financing is necessary for the success, growth, and economic sustainability of small businesses (Włodarczyk et al., 2018). A Fed Small Business (2021) survey showed that 37% of small business owners did not apply for Paycheck Protection Program (PPP) loans because they considered themselves unqualified for the loans and loan forgiveness, and 23% failed to apply because the program was complex and confusing. Small business owners who did not submit PPP applications could not find a lender, pursued alternative financing sources, or did not need the loan.

Loan approval rates vary by lender. Institutions' approval rates for small businesses were 65.9%, with small bank, credit union, and big bank approval rates of 50.3%, 39.7%, and 27.9%, respectively (Statista, 2019). These differences indicate that small business owners' success in acquiring credit differs by loan facility.

The COVID-19 pandemic had a more significant impact on small businesses providing retail and food services than on larger operations (Beauregard et al., 2020). The U.S. SBA examined borrowing during the pandemic, highlighting the lending role of small or community banks as essential to help small businesses survive during the pandemic-associated lockdown. Small business owners need access to credit to sustain operations. Sixty percent of small business owners needing working capital did not apply for PPP assistance, perceiving themselves as unqualified (which aligns with the theory of discouraged borrowers) or finding the process too confusing. The pandemic's impact on small business owners needing credit without strategies to secure it was a topic of conversation with the participants.

Small Businesses and Government Roles

The government also plays an essential role in lending to SMEs. Government leaders worldwide could influence and improve the operation of small businesses through government-initiated subsidies and fiscal policy (Mazzarol & Reboud, 2020). Mazzarol and Reboud (2020) highlighted six areas for government focus when developing policy frameworks to help small businesses: providing business development services, creating business-enabling environments, facilitating market access, promoting innovation and technology use, creating an entrepreneurial culture, and providing access to financing. Personnel at government agencies, such as the U.S. SBA, provide loan guarantees to small businesses and encourage local banks to work with start-ups or established companies wanting to expand.

Legislators could help small businesses through debt and equity financing, credit access, conducive banking regulations, and microfinancing (Mazzarol & Reboud, 2020). Government leaders may enable small business owners to access finance by developing loan guarantee programs (Greene, 2020). Most lenders are reluctant to extend credit facilities to small businesses due to the fear of default; early-stage ventures and small businesses are the most frequent recipients of loan denials. The U.S. government could improve loan access by acting as a guarantor. Government leaders could also promote access to credit for small businesses by offering grants or microloans.

The U.S. SBA's (n.d.) microloan program provides loans of up to \$50,000 to small businesses. Microloan program loans have considerably lower interest rates than loans from other lending institutions, but there are restrictions. The microloan program funds may provide working capital to buy furniture and fixtures, purchase

supplies, meet inventory costs, and acquire equipment and machinery. However, they are not monies for settling existing loans, paying debts, or purchasing real estate. State and federal government legislators have implemented funding options for small businesses, including credit access, favorable banking regulations, debt and equity financing, and microfinancing. Although the participating small business owners may have felt discouraged by other pursuits, some used government resources to obtain working capital for business continuity.

Acquiring Credit

Small business owners' strategies to acquire working capital are a common topic of scholarly inquiry (Ahmed, 2019; Durst & Gerstlberger, 2020; Smith, 2018; Wani, 2018). Durst and Gerstlberger (2020) explored support programs by governments worldwide to facilitate small business enterprises' access to capital. The researchers found significant regional differences in approaches to financing small business enterprises. U.S. government legislators have extensively used loans, equity financing, and surety bonds to promote small business owners' access to financing. In Canada, domestic banks are the leading financing providers. Durst and Gerstlberger concluded that government policies play a critical role in small business owners' acquisition of a line of credit.

Ahmed (2019) conducted a qualitative multiple case study on the strategies of small business owners in Jordan to acquire credit, collecting data via one-on-one interviews. The researcher identified several techniques business owners used to acquire external loans. First, owners focused on developing financial trust to qualify for a loan rather than seeking loans during the businesses' early stages. Another strategy all participants mentioned was improving their financial literacy skills. The eight small business owners also used social networking and information-sharing to understand loan application procedures, terms, and conditions.

Smith (2018) explored small business owners' strategies to secure financing for ongoing operations. Smith used the pecking order theory to explore the strategies used by small business owners in the Southeast United States to secure working capital for continued operations. From a review of company documents and semistructured interviews with six business owners, Smith found participants were more likely to have used personal funds, customer revenue streams, bootstrapping, and personal credit to initially fund their business.

Identifying the strategies used to secure financing could be less important than defining the characteristics of business leaders who succeed in obtaining working capital. Themes from a multiple case study by Wani (2018) were more specific to the owners' traits than their strategic actions. Wani noted the importance of strong entrepreneurial management and financial planning skills in achieving

business continuity, identifying the absence of either skill as a challenge to continuity. Other strengths for business owners to secure funds for continued operations include developing a capital strategy, preparing and adapting to change, and assuming responsibility for creating and maintaining accurate and transparent financial records (Ahmed, 2019; Wani, 2018).

Scholars (e.g., Brooks, 2019) have looked beyond bank financing to uncover other ways for small business owners to sustain operations beyond 5 years. In Brooks’s (2019) study, three small business owners participated in face-to-face, semistructured interviews to discuss strategies they used for business continuity. Data analysis indicated five themes: sufficient start-up funding, access to private lenders, and business owners’ motivation and awareness.

The present study explored small business owners’ strategies for obtaining working capital for business continuity. The participants reported using different strategies, including personal funds, internal financing, debt, and equity. When interviewing small business owners who have secured financing for business operations, a researcher must be aware of the strategies presented in the literature.

Maryland Small Business Development Financing Authority Programs

Commerce incentive funds are a means to help business leaders create jobs, support the local economy, help disadvantaged small businesses, and promote start-up businesses (Maryland Department of Commerce, 2021). In 2016, Maryland’s incentive-based loans exceeded \$90 million. Tax credits and grants are other financial assistance to Maryland small businesses. Small business owners in the state have options to secure financing for business continuity; however, not all owners know what they are. Through an in-depth exploration of financing sources from governments, banks, and lending programs, I found that funding might be more accessible than previously believed. This qualitative exploration of small business leaders’ experiences obtaining working capital showed the use of such programs.

Credit Strategies

Access to external financing is critical to SMEs (Aboojafari et al., 2019) because credit helps their growth (Maini, 2019). SME leaders require external financing when personal resources and retained earnings are inadequate to meet their needs and grow their business (Aboojafari et al., 2019). Access to credit may be challenging for small businesses. Several strategies SME owners use to acquire credit include credit guarantee programs, credit ratings, lending relationships, peer-to-peer lending, and tapping into technology. The small business owners in this study mentioned some of these strategies when discussing how they obtained working capital for business continuity.

Credit Guarantee Schemes

Credit guarantee schemes are strategies to mitigate third-party credit risk to lenders by protecting them against losses due to default (World Bank, 2022a). In recognition of SMEs’ important role in the U.S. economy, the leaders of most governments worldwide have developed credit guarantee schemes for these smaller entities. Several scholars have explored how these schemes facilitate access to credit.

Maini (2019) looked at the role of credit guarantee schemes in financing SMEs in India, finding that the schemes had been incentives for banks to extend credit to SMEs. Wardhono et al. (2019) examined how credit guarantee schemes facilitate credit access by SME owners. The researchers found that owners of SMEs with a credit guarantee were more likely to have access to credit services than those without. Although Corredera-Catalán et al. (2021) also explored the role of credit guarantee programs, they focused on the Spanish guaranteed model, which provides loans based on specific incentives such as sales levels. Data analysis showed that government legislators could use guarantee programs as tools or instruments for improving SME owners’ access to financing. Dang and Chuc (2019) examined the challenges of implementing credit guarantee schemes and the reasons behind the schemes’ poor performance. The findings suggested that credit guarantee schemes did not fulfill their purpose due to strict and impractical conditions, the absence of a credit database, and a lack of adequate professional competence. Small business owners may have used credit guarantee schemes to overcome discouragement and secure working capital for business continuity.

Credit Ratings

Credit ratings are critical in determining SME owners’ ability to access financing. Banks and other lenders rely on credit ratings to determine a debtor’s creditworthiness (Pertaia et al., 2021; Ubarhande & Chandani, 2021). Creditworthiness is the global focal point of credit processing (Ubarhande & Chandani, 2021). Despite standard views of credit ratings as obstacles to accessing credit (Pertaia et al., 2021), ratings may also provide opportunities to access credit. Some small business owners demonstrate creditworthiness by saving money and establishing a good credit history; others avoid or minimize financing to maintain high credit scores (Ahmed, 2019). Scholars have also focused on restructuring credit ratings to improve SMEs’ credit accessibility. Yoshino and Taghizadeh-Hesary (2019) developed a method for assigning credit ratings that lowered the collateral and interest rate requirements.

Access to Capital

The literature revealed some critical concepts regarding small business owners’ access to capital. These

themes included lending relationships, lending during the COVID-19 pandemic, tapping into technology, angel investors, peer-to-peer lending, bootstrapping, and crowdfunding. The following subsections discuss each theme.

Lending Relationships

The relationship between SME owners and lending institutions is a critical determinant in access to capital. In a study of Italian manufacturing firms, Murro and Peruzzi (2022) found that business owners who maintained close and long-lasting relationships with institution lenders could access more credit than owners without such relationships. Business owners' access to credit depended on the information they provided lenders. Ghosh (2019) demonstrated that the relationship between lenders and borrowers was crucial in determining credit accessibility.

Borrowers who maintained long-term relationships with lenders had a greater chance of obtaining credit than those with limited or no relationships. Angori et al. (2019) asserted that the depth and strength of lender–borrower relationships affected credit demand. Angori et al. (2020) found that multiple banking relationships helped alleviate the financial constraints that SME owners face. Following an analysis of the impact of relationships on European firm owners' ability to access credit. The findings showed that relationship approaches to lending improved access to credit and other external financing sources. Ding et al. (2019) suggested that the reputation a borrower builds over time affects lending decisions. This assertion indicates that the longer borrowers can maintain good relationships and reputations, the likelier they are to access loans than business owners with poor reputations.

Lending During the COVID-19 Pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted national global economies (Shafi et al., 2020). SME owners' dependence on bank financing and their inability to raise funds during the pandemic increased the risk of insolvency as businesses faced decreased demand, canceled orders, transportation and supply disruptions, and raw materials shortages (Kalemlı-Ozcan et al., 2020; Shafi et al., 2020). In a survey of small business owners, Bartik et al. (2020) found that 43% of small businesses had closed because of the pandemic, frequently due to reductions in demand, supply chain disruptions, and concerns about employees' health.

Compared to large business leaders, SME owners experienced more significant impacts of the COVID-19 crisis, including mass layoffs and closures (Bartik et al., 2020). The pandemic disproportionately affected SMEs because of their sizes and areas of operation. SME owners have faced more COVID-19 repercussions due to overrepresentation in the hardest-hit sectors, including food service, construction, entertainment, retail, and hospitality (Thukral, 2021). The financial instability of SMEs made them vulnerable to the pandemic's adverse impacts.

The challenges brought by COVID-19 increased SMEs' financial fragility. Bartik et al. (2020) discovered that most SME owners could cover only a fraction of expenses during the pandemic's first few weeks, which likely caused the increase in layoffs and shutdowns. The inability to access credit during the pandemic further worsened SME owners' financial weakness. The pandemic's global nature, severity, and recovery uncertainty further limited SME owners' ability to secure funds, degraded by their lack of collateral (Kalemlı-Ozcan et al., 2020).

Federal and state government leaders introduced legislation to mitigate SMEs' challenges from the COVID-19 pandemic. The Coronavirus Aid, Relief, and Economic Security (CARES) Act was the most significant effort to provide SMEs with financial aid (Bartik et al., 2020). The CARES Act subsequently became part of the PPP.

The growth in pandemic-time lending resulted from small business owners' PPP participation and bank leaders' use of the PPP Liquidity Facility (Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System, 2021). According to data from the first half of 2020, the program increased lending to small businesses and firms during the COVID-19 crisis (U.S. SBA, 2020). Because small business owners' credit needs depend on their relationships with smaller banks, the PPE helped reduce the financial strain on small businesses. In the first half of 2020, small banks played a much more significant role in small business lending, accounting for 25.4%, with medium and larger banks at 22.4% and 52.2%, respectively. These numbers indicate small banks' critical role, providing a quarter of the total lending to small business borrowers (Beauregard et al., 2020).

Tapping Into Technology

Although the impacts of technology remain ambiguous, some scholars have suggested using technology to improve access to credit, as shown by the growth in digital lending. Researchers have explored the role of digital lending in improving access to credit. Johnen et al. (2021) examined digital lending's role in bridging the gap in credit access. Using data from Kenya, the researchers found that digital lending increased borrowing opportunities and reduced individuals' creditworthiness.

Adopting cutting-edge technologies, even if involuntarily, to steer business activities during community lockdowns was often necessary to contain the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic (Akpan et al., 2020). Technologies offer competitive advantages and provide a means for survival. Most business transactions during the COVID-19 pandemic took place online, including applying for loans from state and federal government–provided resources (Díaz de Astarloa et al., 2021). The movement to online transactions affected businesses of all sizes, from SMEs to large operations. Because many SME owners had not yet established online stores and digital sales channels, they had

to collaborate quickly with the delivery platforms to sustain operations. Individuals who use technology to search for financing could find more access to credit. A topic of discussion in participant interviews was whether the small business owners used technology to obtain working capital for business continuity or were discouraged by their nonuse.

Peer-to-Peer Lending

Peer-to-peer lending is another strategy SME owners use to access credit, even those turned down by traditional lenders. After examining the development of peer-to-peer lending in China, Cosgrove and Chowdhury (2021) attributed the growth of peer-to-peer lending to positive outcomes, including different ways of determining creditworthiness. Naysary and Daud (2021) also explored peer-to-peer lending and its economic implications by collecting data from financial technology firms and government sources between 2014 and 2019. The researchers found that such lending was critical to economic growth, improving SME leaders' ability to access credit. Basha et al. (2021) found that most borrowers considered peer-to-peer lending an alternative credit source. Scholars often recommend the implementation of strict regulations in the peer-to-peer lending industry (Basha et al., 2021; Naysary & Daud, 2021).

During the pandemic, the peer-to-peer lending industry received the most significant use of technology and innovation. Using technology during COVID-19 led to improved community and civic spirit. In the United Kingdom and the United States, SME owners, university leaders, and individuals used 3D printers to create personal protective equipment, alleviating shortages during the early stages of the pandemic (Kennesaw State University, 2020). During the COVID-19 pandemic, organizational leaders tested emerging technologies to identify potential new markets and create ways for small business owners to access resources without face-to-face contact. In the present study, small business owners discussed their strategies to obtain working capital for business continuity. Peer-to-peer lending via leveraging relationships was one option this study's participants discussed to minimize discouragement and secure findings.

Angel Investors

Of the two types of external private-party investors—angel investors and venture capitalists—the former usually provide funds during the early stages of the business (McDonald & DeGennaro, 2016). Angel investors contribute money and often their time and expertise to help the small businesses they invest in (Boulton et al., 2019). According to Boulton et al. (2019), angel investors advanced over \$24 billion in 2015. Surveying angel investors in the United Kingdom to understand their views, Harrison et al. (2016) found such investors relied on personal and informal communication to understand their investment risks. The study found that angel investors

preferred business owners to manage agency risk more than market risk to create a good business environment for small business owners.

In studying the behaviors of angel investors, Harrison et al. (2016) found that most patient investors waited to see the return on their investment rather than exiting if their investments did not produce immediate returns. After examining the human capital of angel investors of Belgian companies, Collewaert and Manigart (2016) noted that angel investors with human capital such as level of education, entrepreneurial experience, and professional experience find more value in creating options for their investment opportunities. Venture capitalists invest in high-risk, high-return, and emerging-technology types of businesses (Collewaert & Manigart, 2016), usually funding businesses during the growth period for short-term financial returns (Hsu & Wang, 2014). Venture capitalists are risk-takers for some rewards (Boulton et al., 2019). Bernstein et al. (2016) surveyed venture capitalists and discovered that onsite involvement with portfolio companies resulted in innovation and a successful exit. In Bernstein et al.'s survey, 90% of venture capitalists stated that direct flights to portfolio companies increased their interaction with business leaders. Bocken (2015) discussed the benefits to business leaders working with sustainable venture capitalists who provide advice and triple-bottom-line support to sustainable startup companies: profit, environment, and people. Bocken suggested that sustainable venture capitalists could aid startup businesses in mitigating risk by co-investing and helping leaders balance financial return and social and environmental performances.

Lending by angel investors or venture capitalists depends on institutional factors. Ding et al. (2019) collected data from 27 countries to understand the relationship between institutional factors and investors' decisions. Ding et al. found that institutional factors affected investors' decisions: the rule of law, social trust, and the business's ability to deal with uncertainty.

Bootstrapping

Bootstrapping—acquiring funds without external help, such as using trade credit, customer financing, and financing versus paying upfront—is another way for SMEs to raise funds (Malmström, 2014). Using a survey to examine the influence of bootstrapping on startup companies, Ye (2017) found it negatively affected business revenue growth and profitability. Ye noted that team members' level of education and entrepreneurial experience could provide bootstrapping companies with revenue growth. Miao et al. (2017) examined types of bootstrapping, their measures, and the type of SME performance, finding no correlation between bootstrapping and the financial performance of SMEs. Examining the bootstrapping approach of 120 business founders from Sweden, Winborg (2015) found that such financing positively influenced the

handling of the external liabilities of new businesses. Winborg noted that the bootstrapping approach had no significant impact on the internal liability of new enterprises. Small business owners should be careful using this method to seek working capital.

Trade credit is suitable for preserving on-hand cash, allowing small business leaders to purchase equipment now and pay later (Lawless et al., 2015). Martínez-Sola et al. (2014) identified a positive correlation between trade credit and firms' profitability, recommending that leaders establish a reputation for their firms before seeking trade credit. The established and reputable business owners generated more return from trade credit than those heading up smaller, less liquid firms. Fabbri and Klapper (2016) examined Chinese firms to understand the role of business-client relationships when issuing trade credit, finding that suppliers with weak bargaining power were lenient in granting credit and flexible with payment periods. However, during a credit consultation with a bank, the supplier with weak bargaining power is less likely to issue trade credit. In this case, crowdfunding might be a better option.

Crowdfunding

Crowdfunding is a means for small business owners to raise funds from a large pool of people in small per-person amounts, usually through the internet (Borello et al., 2015). Belleflamme et al. (2014) defined crowdfunding as entrepreneurs raising small funds through many individual contributors. In examining the effect of the social capital of 862 projects on a Chinese crowdfunding platform, Liao et al. (2015) found that the project type moderated the impact of both internal and external social capital. Liao et al. suggested that for-profit company owners' proper use of social capital could improve crowdfunding performance.

Mollick (2014) examined data from over 48,500 projects totaling more than \$237 million in funding to explore the success and failure of crowdfunding ventures, concluding that project quality and personal network affected the crowdfunding success. Belleflamme et al. (2014) compared two types of crowdfunding: preordering of products or services and future profit (equity) sharing. In both types of crowdfunding, business leaders need to build a community of people with whom they interact. The researchers posited that business owners requiring large capital amounts prefer profit sharing. Enterprise leaders seek individual contributors preordering products and services if a capital requirement is small compared to market size.

Information Symmetry in the Lending Process

Information asymmetry occurs when stakeholders have minimal or unequal access to information (Mhlanga, 2021). Information asymmetry causes power imbalances between parties, making transactions less likely. Due to information asymmetry, lenders might struggle to differentiate between high-risk and low-risk borrowers. As a

result, lenders tend to deny credit even to low-risk borrowers.

Scholars have explored the impact of information asymmetry on access to credit. Abdelhadi et al. (2019) found that asymmetry complicated SME financing in Algeria. In another study, Asongu et al. (2019) concluded that integrating information communication technology lessened information asymmetry. The researchers found that reductions in information asymmetry led to reduced loan prices and increased loan amounts.

Audited Financial Statements

Audited financial statements show a firm's performance over time (Otuya et al., 2019). The accounting information provided by would-be borrowers affects lending decisions (Aifuwa et al., 2019). In a study of Nigerian manufacturing firms, Aifuwa et al. (2019) found that providing accounting information affected owners' ability to access loans, with a visible monetary value of collateral positively impacting banks' lending decisions. Otuya et al. (2019) determined that financial information and statements were critical for lenders to determine firms' performance and ability to access credit. SME owners face challenges in maintaining financial records (Aladejebi & Oladimeji, 2019) and often struggle to access credit (Aifuwa et al., 2019). Small business owners demonstrate the accuracy of their recorded profits and losses by providing audited financial statements to lenders.

The State of the Economy at the Time of This Study

A new economic threat emerged in the second quarter of 2020: the COVID-19 global pandemic. Although the long-term impact of the COVID-19 pandemic is unknown, early responses were alternately encouraging and disheartening (DePietro, 2020; Dunkelberg, 2020). Positive outcomes have included low-interest or interest-free lines of credit, higher lines of credit, waived late fees, and deferred payments. The onset of COVID-19 increased the need for small business credit, as indicated by the demand for government-provided financial assistance. U.S. legislators introduced financial aid through small business loans to pay employees' salaries while businesses were not operating, with many loans forgivable. The \$370 billion PPP ran out of funds after just 14 days (Ransom, 2020, para. 2), with only 20% of applications processed (Dunkelberg, 2020, para. 4). Congress approved a second round of small business loans of \$310 billion, 40% of which was still available 2 weeks after launch (Green, 2020; Hayashi, 2020). The impact of the pandemic on small businesses in 2020 and beyond is unknown (Kukura, 2020).

Amid the COVID-19 pandemic, business leaders adjusted their activities to utilize available tools and implement innovative promotion processes. As the impact of COVID-19 intensified globally, business leaders used open innovation tools, such as knowledge-sharing, networking, and technology acquisition, to help manage their work teams

and communicate more effectively during challenging and uncertain times (Harel, 2021). SME owners derive revenues primarily from subcontracting, business-to-business work, and long-term agreements (Tudormeau et al., 2018). Although small businesses often fare better during economic difficulty and uncertainty (Harel, 2021), the COVID-19 pandemic was an unprecedented economic catastrophe.

Small businesses were the most severely affected by the pandemic. SMEs, such as those in the retail and service industry, are typically more credit-constrained than larger operations (Cao & Leung, 2020; Kumar & Francisco, 2005). Industry-sector small businesses often operate in niche and highly specific markets (Wong & Aspinwall, 2004). Many large company leaders subcontract small businesses to incorporate specialized skills and perform tasks outside their core business (Tudormeau et al., 2018). In the United States, most companies are small businesses responsible for a substantial share of employment (Humphries et al., 2020). Small business owners in Maryland facing continued COVID-19 financial impacts were eligible for support from the Maryland government through the 2021 COVID-19 RELIEF Grant Program, which delivered \$10 million in funding. The grant provided working capital to assist qualifying Maryland small businesses with disrupted operations due to COVID-19.

The COVID-19 pandemic impacted economies worldwide, and small businesses were particularly hard hit. Some businesses closed, at least temporarily, due to community lockdowns and government restrictions. Although securing credit is imperative for business continuity, it became increasingly challenging. Although the Maryland small business owners in this study had obtained working capital for business continuity for at least five years, the economy likely impacted their businesses.

Growth in Lending During COVID-19

The growth in lending during the pandemic was due to small business owners' PPP participation and bank lenders' use of the PPP liquidity facility. Data from the first half of 2020 showed that these programs contributed to lending growth during the pandemic, particularly small banks (U.S. SBA, 2020). The programs led to increased lending to SMEs during the COVID-19 pandemic, a necessary outcome based on SME leaders' dependency on relationships with smaller banks to meet their credit needs. The programs also helped reduce the financial strain on small businesses. Small banks played a much more significant role in the first half of 2020, providing 25.4% of the lending to small businesses (U.S. SBA, 2020).

SME leaders have embraced innovation and invention to reduce the negative impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. New technologies (e.g., the Internet of Things, blockchain) and innovations (e.g., digitization) allow businesses to function, develop, and work in a continuously changing environment (Borowski, 2021). During the

pandemic, SME owners adopted the product, process, marketing, and organizational innovations (OECD, n.d.). Gopalakrishnan and Kovoov-Misra (2021) developed an approach to classify innovations during the COVID-19 pandemic, categorizing them as threat-driven and opportunity-driven. Whereas threat-driven innovation was reactive, opportunity-driven innovations were proactive. Despite differences among innovation change processes, product productions, marketing, and organizational practices, each approach aided the COVID-19 response. Innovations and technologies enabled SME owners to handle the negative impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The scope of the pandemic's impact on the revenue of industrial-sector small businesses depended on many factors. The extent to which small business owners made changes in operations and activities, utilized open innovation tools, and implemented managerial processes helped them sustain operations during the pandemic. Small business owners who implemented business activity changes or adjustments during the pandemic had reduced expenses compared to business owners who did not change or adjust. During the pandemic, lender and borrower PPP participation was critical to lending growth. In line with the 2020 and 2021 literature, the small business owners in this study could have changed their operations to obtain working capital for business continuity.

Minimizing Business Expenses to Forestall Loans

By minimizing their costs and operations, small business owners may decrease their need to obtain external financing for continued operations. Many business publications and professional organizations (e.g., *Harvard Business Review*, *Forbes*, American Express) have provided guidelines for reducing businesses' operational costs. Guidance specific to small business owners includes pursuing technology, outsourcing, leasing, negotiating arrangements with suppliers, and creating a budget plan (FNCB Bank, n.d.). Small business owners may postpone new customer acquisitions and concentrate on client retention until their financial situation stabilizes.

Thorgren and Williams (2020) analyzed data collected from 456 SMEs in Norrbotten, Sweden, during the COVID-19 pandemic. The primary means of minimizing costs reported by the participants were deferring investments, reducing labor costs, and cutting expenses. The participants reported owners, board members, and higher-ups working without or with a reduced salary, taking on more hours, and eliminating nonessential activities and pursuits. Despite the timing of Thorgren and Williams' study, the findings remain applicable to all small business owners.

Transition

More than half of U.S. companies meet the definition of small businesses with fewer than 500

employees (U.S. SBA Office of Advocacy, 2020), and nearly 50% fail to operate beyond 5 years (Small Business & Entrepreneurship Council, 2016). The problem is that some small business owners lack strategies to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond 5 years. In this qualitative descriptive multiple case study, I explored strategies that small business owners used to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond 5 years. The pecking order theory (Myers & Majluf, 1984) was the conceptual framework to explore small business owners' perceptions when acquiring working capital to ensure business continuity. The literature review in Section 1 pertained to the research topic of small businesses, including opportunities and challenges, types of credit available to small business leaders, information symmetry in the lending process, and credit strategies.

Section 2 includes a detailed analysis of the research method, design, and support for why the selected approach was suitable for the study. I discuss participant selection, the role of the researcher, ethical considerations, and the data collection, organization, and analysis procedures. Concluding Section 2 in a review of the study's reliability and validity. Section 3 presents the findings compared to those of previous scholarly studies. I also discuss how my findings apply to professional practice, social change implications, and recommendations for action and further research. Section 3 concludes with a reflection on my experiences in the DBA program.

SECTION 2: THE PROJECT

Section 2 presents the research method and design, justification of the number of participants, the role of the researcher, and adherence to ethical standards. It also contains information regarding the data collection, organization, and analysis approaches. The section concludes with a discussion of actions taken to ensure research reliability and validity.

Purpose Statement

This qualitative descriptive multiple case study explored strategies that small business owners used to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond 5 years. The sample was eight small business owners in Maryland who had obtained working capital for business continuity. An implication for social change is that small business owners may be able to sustain operations, thus providing employment opportunities that could increase citizens' standard of living and contribute to their well-being in the local communities. Another implication for social change is that sustaining small business operations will allow customers to continue receiving the products and services they need, contributing to their quality of life and the sustainability of their household or business operations.

Role of the Researcher

A qualitative researcher is responsible for all stages of the data collection process. I interviewed eight small business owners who obtained working capital for business continuity. Because the researcher is the primary data collection instrument in qualitative studies (McGrath et al., 2019), I was the data collection instrument in this study. I used semistructured interviews with open-ended questions to obtain detailed information from participants. Although I planned to collect data from participant-provided company documents, COVID-19 protocols, and virtual interviews enabled only a brief look.

As a career credit union banker with 20 years of experience underwriting small business loans, I have personal experience and expertise on the topic and research area. To reduce the likelihood of bias, I remained objective, followed an interview protocol, and did not let my professional position conflict with my role as a researcher despite my relationships with banking and business associations and affiliations. With my extensive understanding of the phenomenon under study, suspending prejudice and staying objective to achieve trustworthy findings was especially important.

Researchers must adhere to the ethical guidelines outlined in *The Belmont Report* (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979) and *Ethics in Research with Human Participants* (Sales & Folkman, 2000). I maintained respect, beneficence, and justice for all participants. I separated my professional role as a small business lending consultant and my researcher role of soliciting and interviewing small business owners.

An interview protocol (see Appendix A) provided a guide for each interview, with each participant answering seven questions in the same order. An interview protocol is a uniform way for a researcher to gather comparable participant data (Devotta et al., 2016). I developed an interview protocol comprised of predetermined questions and an outline to maintain consistency throughout the interviews. Following the protocol ensured a standardized process with each participant to mitigate bias in the interviewing process.

Participants

To be eligible for the study, individuals had to be business owners of small manufacturing and wholesale businesses in Maryland with 500 or fewer employees. Participants must have used successful strategies to obtain working capital for business continuity. Because of my professional experience as a credit union banker underwriting loans for small and medium-sized enterprises, I asked some small business owners I knew to refer participants for the study.

I used a partnership agreement to ensure cooperation from the chosen organizations (see Appendix

B). I established a working relationship with prospective participants through telephone or email contact (see DeJonckheere & Vaughn, 2019). Upon connecting with qualified individuals, I discussed the purpose of the study, including the participation process and implications for business practice. I developed a rapport with the participants to determine if they qualified for the study and offered to answer any questions. I continued to call potentially qualified individuals until I obtained eight small business owners who met the appropriate criteria and were willing to participate in the study.

Research Method and Design

Research Method

The research method and design are blueprints for connecting research elements to exploring questions and drawing conclusions (Leedy & Ormrod, 2013). Qualitative researchers describe participants' experiences (Baškarada, 2014; Sandelowski, 1997; Yin, 2017) instead of using numbers to explain phenomena of interest (Landrum & Garza, 2015; White et al., 2012). Qualitative methodology enables a researcher to understand a particular occurrence from the perspective of those who have experienced it (Baškarada, 2014; Sandelowski, 1997; Vaismoradi et al., 2013; Yin, 2017). Exhaustive qualitative research involves descriptively exploring the experiences of participants through self-awareness or interactive interpretation to frame a need for change or reform (T. L. Walker & Taylor, 2014). The basis of qualitative research is comparing views according to different realities (Bahari, 2012). The qualitative method was the most appropriate for this study to explore the phenomenon of eight small business owners who succeeded in obtaining working capital.

I considered and rejected quantitative and mixed methods approaches. Researchers use quantitative methodology to produce generalizable findings, test the relationships and differences between variables and constructs, and test hypotheses (Landrum & Garza, 2015; Parry et al., 2014; Yin, 2017). Quantitative research involves analyzing identified variables to determine a correlation, significance, or relationship and testing theories using hypotheses (Antonakis et al., 2014; Westerman, 2014). Quantitative researchers focus on analyzing statistical data rather than obtaining information on participants' experiences, mindsets, or strategies (Thamhain, 2014). The quantitative method did not align with the purpose of this study; therefore, I rejected that approach.

A mixed methods approach enables the integration of qualitative and quantitative data in a single study (Petticrew et al., 2013). Researchers using mixed methods gather distinct contributions from qualitative and quantitative research methodologies (Bryman & Bell, 2015; Fetters & Molina-Azorin, 2017; McCusker & Gunaydin, 2015). Because quantitative methodology did not align with

the purpose of this study, a mixed methods approach was inappropriate.

Research Design

I used a case study design for this study. A case study design enables a researcher to frame one or more cases in real-life settings to explore a phenomenon holistically and deeply (Marshall & Rossman, 2016; Merriam, 1998; Yin, 2017). A case study researcher answers the central research question from the perspectives of individuals with direct experience with the concept. The qualitative case study approach was optimal for this study to explore a phenomenon in a real-life context.

Other qualitative research designs include ethnography, phenomenology, and narrative (Marshall & Rossman, 2016; Miles et al., 2014; Onwuegbuzie et al., 2012). Ethnographic researchers explore and analyze a problem contextualized through observations and interviews within a historical and cultural setting (Marshall & Rossman, 2016; Vesa & Vaara, 2014) to understand the values, language, and beliefs of a culture, group, or individual (Marshall & Rossman, 2016; Robinson, 2014). Phenomenology entails participants describing personal lived experiences, perspectives, or knowledge of a problem concretely without abstract generalization (Marshall & Rossman, 2016; J. L. Walker, 2012). Phenomenological researchers explore the essence of participant experience via interviews and observations (Kafle, 2013; Marshall & Rossman, 2016). Using narrative inquiry, researchers collect data through observation, documentation, questionnaires, interviews, photos, or artifacts to contextualize participant experience (Marshall & Rossman, 2016; Petty et al., 2012). Narrative studies allow investigators to delve deeply into participants' life experiences and contextualize their understanding of the problem under study (Marshall & Rossman, 2016; Venkatesh et al., 2013). Because I did not explore cultures, seek concrete descriptions of lived experiences, or contextualize participant experiences, I rejected ethnography, phenomenology, and narrative designs in favor of the case study approach.

To obtain trustworthy and credible findings, a qualitative researcher must achieve data saturation (DeJonckheere & Vaughn, 2019; Fusch & Ness, 2015). Failure to reach saturation threatens the study's quality, reliability, and validity (Nelson & Squires, 2017). Saturation occurs when continued data collection and analysis reveals recurring themes with no new ideas emerging (Constantinou et al., 2017; O'Reilly & Parker, 2013; J. L. Walker, 2012). I confirmed data saturation when no new themes emerged as I coded and thematically analyzed data from participant interviews.

Population and Sampling

The participants in this case study were eight small business owners in Maryland who obtained working capital

for business continuity. The two key considerations that guide sampling in qualitative research are appropriateness and adequacy in answering the research questions (O’Reilly & Parker, 2013). Purposive sampling allows researchers to solicit participants based on their knowledge of the phenomenon under study (Barratt et al., 2015; Petty et al., 2012; Yin, 2017). I created a list of additional potential participants to ensure I obtained at least six usable interviews, ultimately recruiting eight small business owners. Purposive sampling was the best way to explore the strategies used by small business owners to obtain working capital within a changing business environment.

Eligible participants met the following criteria: (a) owned a small manufacturing and wholesale business in Maryland, (b) employed 500 or fewer people, and (c) used successful strategies to obtain working capital for business continuity. Interviews take place in what participants determine to be a private and comfortable place (McGrath et al., 2019). I allowed participants to choose the date and time of the interviews, which occurred virtually via Zoom.

Unlike quantitative research, there are no predetermined sample sizes in qualitative studies. Creswell and Creswell (2018) recommended five to six cases for a case study. Kuzel (1992) suggested a homogeneous sample with six to eight interviews. Hagaman and Wutich (2017) proposed interviewing up to 16 individuals in qualitative research. Based on these recommendations, I selected eight as an appropriate sample size for this study.

In qualitative inquiry, the aim is not to acquire a specific number of participants but to gather enough in-depth information to describe the phenomenon fully and to reach data saturation (O’Reilly & Parker, 2013). The sample size is less important than the ability to elicit rich, thick data to achieve saturation (Fusch & Ness, 2015). Data saturation occurs when continued data collection generates no new information (Fusch & Ness, 2015), evidencing rigor in qualitative research (Constantinou et al., 2017). I planned for saturation by developing a solid study, purposively sampling participants who could provide the data needed to answer the research question, and selecting more participants than recommended by Creswell and Creswell (2018) and Kuzel (1992). Data saturation occurred when no new information emerged from coding and thematically analyzing participant interview data.

Ethical Research

Informed consent is a necessary component of ethical research to ensure participants know what a study entails, their right to confidentiality and fair treatment, and the voluntary nature of participation. When the invited business owners agreed to take part in the study, I emailed them an informed consent form outlining the details of the study, the risks and benefits of participation, their right to withdraw without penalty at any time before data analysis, and any incentives for participation. Before each interview, I

reviewed the informed consent form with the participants and answered their questions. Participants provided signed consent to the audio recording. As noted in the consent form, the risks associated with participation were minimal and included only the feelings related to the recalled information. Although there were no direct benefits to participation, the information gleaned from this study may help other small business owners obtain working capital for continued operations. At any point in the study, the participants could have emailed my Walden University address listed on the informed consent form if they chose to withdraw their participation. Upon receipt of such notification, I would have immediately shredded any material related to the participant, deleted any audio recordings, and removed any collected or analyzed data from consideration. However, no participants withdrew from the study.

I maintained the highest values in academic research regarding the ethical protection of participants. Respect for participants entails providing transparency in the research process and objectives. I conducted my study per the requirement of ethical research under Walden University Institutional Review Board (IRB) Approval No. 08-02-23-0559319. Ethical standards require ensuring participants’ protection and confidentiality. Before each interview, I reassured participants that their identities would remain confidential. I used alphanumeric codes instead of names on all research data (e.g., P1, P2, etc.), including interview recordings, handwritten notes, transcribed interview responses, NVivo files, and research write-ups. No names appear in the final study to protect participants’ identities.

Data archiving is another ethical consideration that involves securing, preserving, and storing research data and resources for a future audit, enabling others to verify findings or advance research (Corti, 2012). I password-protected and stored all data—including signed informed consent forms, electronic documents, handwritten notes, and transcribed interview responses—on a password-protected thumb drive, which I will retain in a secure, fireproof vault for 5 years. After that time, I will erase and destroy the files.

Data Collection Instrument

In qualitative studies, a researcher serves as the instrument for data collection (Leedy & Ormrod, 2013). Thus, I was the data collection instrument in this study. I used a partnership agreement to ensure cooperation from the participating organizations (see Appendix B). I gathered data through semistructured interviews to understand small business owners’ strategies for acquiring working capital. An interview protocol (see Appendix A) served as a guide for the one-on-one semistructured interviews with open-ended questions. Using an interview protocol ensures the researcher asks the same basic questions of all participants (Yin, 2017). Open-ended questions provide an opportunity for follow-up queries or probing. The interview protocol

included an introduction, interview questions, follow-up probing questions, an interview wrap-up, appreciation, and the scheduling of the follow-up member-checking interview.

Some researchers allow participants to review transcripts of their interviews to clarify their answers or provide additional information (Harvey, 2015). Other scholars prefer member checking, which enables participants to confirm the collected data's accuracy and enhance credibility and validity (Cope, 2014; Harper & Cole, 2012; Harvey, 2015). Instead of transcript reviews, the participants engaged in member checking by reviewing my interpretations of the data to enhance the study's reliability and validity.

Data Collection Technique

This study's two data collection techniques were semistructured interviews and document reviews. One-on-one semistructured interviews occurred via Zoom at the participants' convenience. I followed a predetermined interview protocol (see Appendix A) as a procedural guide for what to do and say. Before I began each interview, I reviewed the informed consent form with participants, which they electronically signed, and asked for questions before I began the interview. Seven open-ended questions comprised the interview protocol, ensuring each participant received and responded to the same questions. The open-ended questions allowed me to pose any probing, or follow-up queries necessary to obtain sufficient information to answer the research question. I used conversational language and industry-specific jargon to create a relaxed environment and support follow-up responses.

By signing the informed consent form, the eight small business owners consented to participate and allow me to audio record the interviews. Audio recording and transcribing interviews are superior to relying solely on manually documented notes, which might be open to interpretation and distract the researcher during interview sessions (Oltmann, 2016). Audio recording ensured the accurate capture of participants' responses.

Collecting data from semistructured interviews has advantages and disadvantages. Conducting one-on-one semistructured interviews lets researchers keep an open mind, enabling concepts and theories to emerge from the data inductively (Jenner & Myers, 2019). The flexibility of semistructured interviews allows a researcher to refocus the conversation or prompt for more information as needed to obtain quality data sufficient to answer the research question (Baškarada, 2014; Bearman, 2019; Low, 2019). By asking open-ended questions, interviewers give participants discretion in responding (Bearman, 2019).

A disadvantage of semistructured interviews is the potential to miss unexpected or surprising evidence (Baškarada, 2014). An inductive approach to theorizing and conceptualizing allows participants to answer interview questions less explicitly than in more structured research

(Bryman & Bell, 2015). Common threats to compelling interviews include misinterpreting or misunderstanding questions and answers (e.g., due to personal prejudices or convictions), asking leading or loaded questions, interjecting comments that could bias the response, listening only to what is easy to understand, and making assumptions based on prior responses (Baškarada, 2014).

Documents could be a valuable part of research and may be helpful for systematic evaluation to elicit meaning and understand the business processes used (Bowen, 2009). During our initial qualifying meeting, I asked each small business owner for any supporting documents that were not proprietary or confidential. The documents included publicly available products or services, service areas, mission and vision statements, or articles of incorporation filed with the Maryland Secretary of State. However, I obtained only glimpses of the participants' documents because the interviews occurred virtually.

Researchers use member checking to improve the trustworthiness of their findings (Amin et al., 2020; Stahl & King, 2020), thus affirming the accuracy and credibility of the study (DeCino & Waalkes, 2019). After analyzing the data and identifying themes, I scheduled a second meeting with the participants to perform member checking. I presented my interpretations of the interviews and findings to ensure they were correct. If they believed I had misrepresented or misinterpreted their words, I would have corrected and updated my interpretations; however, all participants agreed with the findings.

Data Organization Technique

I maintained a separate and organized database comprising data, research logs, reflexive journal, and organizational documents. This information will allow others to inspect the raw data that led to my conclusions. Without a case study database, commingling case study narratives with data interpretations could render inspecting raw data nearly impossible (Yin, 2017).

I imported all interview responses into NVivo 14 for storage and organization. NVivo enables the creation of charts, graphs, word clouds, and other visual aids to assist in managing data and capturing emerging understanding. I maintained a research log, documenting the study processes to provide a detailed audit trail for subsequent replication. I also kept a reflective journal to record my thoughts, impressions, and opinions, checking for personal bias as needed.

Maintaining data safety, security, confidentiality, and accessibility is the foremost objective in data storage (Whitlock et al., 2010). All study files, including emails, interviews, journals, notes, audio recordings, and references, will remain securely stored in a fire-, water-, and theft-proof safe for 5 years, with the electronic data stored on a password-protected thumb drive. I will shred and delete all raw data after that time.

Data Analysis

Data analysis began after the completion of all interviews. I reviewed the data from semistructured interviews, and the documents provided by participants via Zoom screen sharing. Data triangulation entails analyzing multiple data sources to identify common findings and enhance a study’s trustworthiness (Whitmore et al., 2019), which was appropriate for this study. After importing and coding the data in NVivo, I detected themes from the two sources.

Researchers use data triangulation to increase the trustworthiness of their findings (Whitmore et al., 2019). Triangulation entails analyzing multiple data sources. I collected data from two sources: semistructured interviews and documents briefly shared by the participants or obtained via searches of the U.S. SBA website. I coded each data set individually (disassembled) and then compared my codes (reassembled) to confirm the findings. I followed Yin’s (2017) five-phase data analysis process of compiling, disassembling, reassembling, interpreting, and concluding.

Compiling

Yin’s (2017) first phase is compiling and pulling together all data sources for analysis. After transcribing the interview recordings, I reviewed the shared documents for parallels. I imported both sets of data into NVivo 14 for analysis.

Disassembling

In the second phase, I disassembled the data by reading and rereading the transcripts, looking for meaningful words and noting their alignment with the research question. Researchers disassemble data by dividing them into manageable pieces to reconstruct and reflect a view of reality (Yin, 2017). I highlighted relevant words, phrases, and similarities in the data, a process known as coding. I looked for patterns in the data, comparing the participants’ responses. I then revisited the study’s purpose and determined how the data answered the research question.

Reassembling

In the third phase, I performed a context analysis and conducted a second round of coding. Reassembling is a means of creating themes from the disassembled data (Yin, 2017). I looked for categories and patterns and performed comparisons, merging the data into relevant themes. As I viewed the data, I checked that they made sense and related to the study’s concept.

Interpreting

I interpreted the data by describing the emerging themes. According to Yin (2017), interpreting is a process where the researcher becomes familiar with the meaning of the data. I narrowed these descriptions to correlate with the research question. In this phase, I also considered the validity and credibility of my interpretation.

Concluding

After I interpreted the data, I grouped the data into conclusions. Yin’s (2017) fifth phase involves concluding the data. I determined how the study’s key themes or findings aligned with the conceptual framework and supported current literature. Finally, I prepared for the presentation of the findings.

Reliability and Validity

Reliability and validity are critical to scientific rigor, ensuring researchers meet the highest standards of academic research (Noble & Smith, 2015). Qualitative trustworthiness is the equivalent of quantitative validity and reliability (Cope, 2014). Quantitative reliability parallels qualitative dependability, whereas quantitative validity applies to qualitative credibility, transferability, and confirmability (Cope, 2014; Morse, 2015). All components are necessary for trustworthiness (Miles et al., 2014).

Reliability

A study is dependable if later researchers can repeat the procedures and find the same results (Baškarada, 2014; Guba, 1981; Yin, 2017). I maintained a detailed audit trail of study processes to enable replication, improving dependability. Another means of increasing dependability was using two data sources. I kept a researcher reflexivity journal to ensure the findings I presented came from participants’ responses and not my perspectives (see Korstjens & Moser, 2018). I employed member checking, having the participants check that my interview interpretations were reliable.

Validity

A qualitative study has validity if the findings demonstrate credibility, transferability, and confirmability (Megheirkouni & Moir, 2023). Researchers must ensure saturation to elicit all themes from the collected data.

Credibility

Credibility refers to the objectivity and impartiality of research findings (Bradshaw et al., 2017), meaning they accurately reflect participants’ opinions and perspectives (Colorafi & Evans, 2016). I was responsible for maintaining research rigor and enhancing study credibility, which I improved through data triangulation. I also used member checking, asking participants to review my interpretations of the data.

Transferability

I took steps to enhance transferability. Transferability is the extent to which a study’s findings apply to other contexts or settings (Pozzebon et al., 2014). I followed the sampling, data collection, and data analysis procedures as outlined and appropriate to the case study design. I used an interview protocol to ensure all participants received the same questions. Another means of improving transferability is an audit trail, keeping in-depth, detailed documentation of the steps undertaken in the study, from recruitment to the presentation of findings (Merriam,

1998; Morse, 2015). I maintained an audit trail throughout the study, from conceptualization and participant selection to data analysis and findings. The audit trail provides a detailed outline that future scholars could apply to similar populations or situations to achieve similar findings. I recognize that researchers and readers will determine the transferability of my findings.

Confirmability

Another component of research quality, confirmability, is the truthfulness and correctness of a study's findings without researcher bias (Elo et al., 2014; Nowell et al., 2017; Yin, 2017). I asked probing questions during participant interviews to explore their responses and ensure understanding. I followed the outlined procedures to ensure data accuracy and used member checking to enhance confirmability. I conducted member-checking interviews with the participants to verify that my initial interpretations of the data were accurate. A peer reviewer looked over my findings for accuracy, improving the study's confirmability.

Data Saturation

Data saturation in qualitative research entails collecting data from multiple sources and techniques until no new information emerges (Guest et al., 2006). Data saturation contributes to a study's validity (Megheirkouni & Moir, 2023). I achieved data saturation when no new themes emerged from coding and thematically analyzing data from participant interviews and documents.

Transition and Summary

In Section 2, I presented the data analysis procedures in accordance with the research method and design. I discussed the role of the researcher as a data collection instrument and described the participants and the sampling method. I presented the data collection instruments and data collection and organization techniques. Finally, I outlined the data analysis procedures for compiling, disassembling, reassembling, and interpreting and addressed the study's reliability and validity.

This qualitative descriptive multiple case study aimed to explore strategies small business owners use to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond 5 years. Section 3 includes a restatement of the study's purpose and descriptions of the role of the researcher, the participants, the research method and design, the population and sampling methods, ethical research, data collection sources and techniques, data organization and analysis, and reliability and validity. Section 3 presents the findings,

application to professional practice, implications for social change, recommendations for action and further research, researcher reflections, and a conclusion.

SECTION 3: APPLICATION TO PROFESSIONAL PRACTICE AND IMPLICATIONS FOR CHANGE

This qualitative, multiple case study explored small business owners' strategies to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond 5 years. Section 3 begins with the findings and themes that emerged from interviews with eight small business owners in Maryland. There are discussions of applications to professional practice, implications for social change, recommendations for action and further research, and personal reflections, followed by a conclusion.

Presentation of the Findings

Qualitative methodology and a multiple case study design were appropriate to elicit the insight needed to answer the research question: What strategies do small business owners use to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond 5 years? Eight small business owners participated in one-on-one semistructured interviews via Zoom. To ensure confidentiality, I used alphanumeric codes instead of names (e.g., P1, P2, P3 ...). Due to COVID-19 restrictions, I could not view company documents in person. Although some participants presented documents via Zoom screen sharing to support their statements, I was unable to review the material thoroughly. Because I did not acquire the participants' financial data, I searched publicly available documents to support this study. I located three pertinent documents on the U.S. SBA website: (D1) financial statements, (D2) investment performance, and (D3) financial portfolios.

I used NVivo 14 qualitative coding software to identify similar words and phrases and manually reviewed the data for redundancy, accuracy, and theme identification. In line with a multiple case study design, this thematic data analysis approach provided an enhanced understanding of the phenomenon and the participants' experiences. Five major themes emerged from coding: (a) financing through retained earnings, (b) financing through nontraditional lending sources, (c) external funding not readily accessible in earlier years, (d) external financing used at later and critical stages of business, and (e) minimizing business operational costs and expenses (see Table 1). The themes are discussed in the following subsections.

Table 1. Main Themes and Frequencies

Themes	<i>n</i> participants referencing the theme	<i>n</i> times referenced
1. Financing through retained earnings	8	8
2. Financing through nontraditional lending sources	7	19
3. External funding not readily accessible in earlier years	7	16
4. External financing used at later and critical stages of business	6	21
5. Minimizing business operational costs and expenses	4	13

Theme 1: Financing Through Retained Earnings

The eight small business owners interviewed in this study identified retained earnings as the most common financing approach. Most participants used this option to sustain operations and borrow as little as possible, especially in the first 5 years. P2 and P4 reported using 90% internal financing to incur minimal debt. P2 said, “It makes the most sense to use business profits first. External financing is the last resort.” P4 responded, “By using retained earnings, I avoided paying unnecessary interest charges.” Most participants preferred using business earnings (Theme 1) and personal financing (Theme 2 subtheme), with two drawing almost exclusively from company funds.

Because retained earnings are the most accessible, least risky, and most cost-effective means of obtaining needed capital, small business owners used this funding source first. Processes to obtain external financing through traditional lending sources, such as banks, do not exist when using internal funding. With low or zero interest, internal funding has less risk and cost than other financing sources. P3 elaborated on cost as a factor in choosing the source of financing, saying, “Each of these funding sources has associated costs, one more than the other. So, what I try to do is first utilize the cheapest one, of course. The cheapest one is my capital, so we use that first.”

Connecting Theme 1 to the Literature and Conceptual Framework

Theme 1 supported the literature, showing a preference for internal financing. Small business owners prefer to operate for extended periods without debt financing (Mazzarol & Reboud, 2020). Given the financial implications of different funding sources, small business owners typically prefer to use lower-cost funds, such as retained earnings (*n* = 5), which aligns with the pecking

order theory’s preference for funding sources (Myers & Majluf, 1984). This finding aligned with Dhaene et al. (2017), who discovered that small business owners preferred using retained earnings before pursuing debt options. In Zeidan et al.’s (2018) study, company leaders opted to use retained earnings over subsidized loans.

Theme 1 aligned with the pecking order theory, which indicates a preference for internal funding (Myers & Majluf, 1984). Myers (1984) explained the pecking order theory as a preference for using lower-cost internal funding over external financing. Five participants discussed profit reinvestment to raise capital and sustain operations.

Theme 2: Financing Through Nontraditional Lending Sources

The participants reported employing less traditional efforts to minimize debt in their financing choices. Personal resources were common funding sources. P8 stated,

The first 5 years was personal funding, mainly personal funding. We didn’t refinance our house like some entrepreneurs do. We chose not to do that. We used personal savings, withdrew from our 401(k), and [drew from] any other funds we could get.

P1 used self-funding to raise capital and sustain operations. In some instances, the participants preferred personal borrowing due to their inability to raise funds from other sources. P2 mentioned applying for a loan, receiving a rejection, and turning to her family to help sustain her business. Across the participants, nontraditional financing sources included personal funds (*n* = 8), personal borrowing (*n* = 5), family and spousal savings (*n* = 4), franchising and payment plans (*n* = 4), and contribution schemes (*n* = 1). Table 2 shows the subthemes within Theme 2.

Table 2

Theme 2: Financing Through Nontraditional Lending Sources – Subthemes

Subthemes	<i>n</i> participants referencing the theme	<i>n</i> times referenced
Personal funds	2	2
Personal borrowing	5	9
Family–spousal savings	4	6
Franchising and payment plans	4	5
Contribution schemes	1	1

Note. *N* = 8.

Subtheme 1: Personal Funds

All participants reported accessing personal funds or savings as a means of financing business operations, which they identified as an easy internal funding strategy. The business owners discussed using their investments, savings, and salaries from the company and other jobs. P4 responded, “It was mostly savings. I utilized my saved funds.” Some participants had side jobs and external salaries in their businesses’ early stages. P1 said,

For the most part, the way that I have funded my business to minimize debt is to work extra hours or take on side jobs. Because of my training as a physician, I’m a high-income earner, so it’s easy for me to raise funds by working extra hours.

P1 stated, “Most of our capital has been self-funded.”

Subtheme 2: Personal Borrowing

Five of the eight participants reported using financing options that required personal borrowing. The sources included withdrawals from their retirement plans, including 401(k) and IRA accounts. Other means of financing were credit cards and home equity loans. P1 reported drawing from retirement monies to maintain business continuity. The participant said, “When I have [a] need to fund anything, I take out money from my IRA and my 401(k) accounts.”

Some participants relied on credit or home equity for business funding. In some situations, the business owners obtained money from their or their family members’ credit limits and credit cards. P2 stated, “When I have required short-term funds, I have to use my son’s credit to access funding.” P3 recalled, “We didn’t borrow much. It was just personal savings, taking money out from our 401(k) accounts, using simple stuff like credit cards to purchase items ... required to operate the business.” One participant reported drawing from his home’s equity to finance his business. P3 said, “We have used, within the last 3 to 4 years, refinancing of our assets, such as accessing a home equity loan.” The five participants who reported the use of debt-based internal financing drew from a variety of sources, including personal funds, retirement accounts, home equity, personal and family credit, and credit cards,

Subtheme 3: Family–Spousal Savings

Four participants mentioned using family or spousal savings to fund their businesses in the early stages. In some cases, personal funds were necessary due to the inability to obtain external financing. P2 said, “I actually tried to get a loan, but I didn’t succeed. So, in my first year or so, I relied on family money.” Other participants reported using personal monies to start the business. P6 stated, “We commenced operations in 2013 utilizing initial equity from family. So about 40% of startup capital was from family funds.”

Subtheme 4: Franchising and Payment Plans

Four participants used franchising and payment plans to fund their businesses. P8 said, “One of the strategies I used to finance my business was to join a franchise.” Franchising is an attractive means of growing a business (Watson, 2008), enabling an owner to procure inventory easily and lease much of the required equipment. To purchase high-value equipment, P1 and P6 developed payment plans with other companies. P6 explained, “Our suppliers allowed us to spread out repayment over a period of time to avoid having to apply for bank loans.” P1 reported, “Spreading out payments allowed me to use internally generated cash flow.” The participant continued,

It’s only when we need to make a capital purchase that we seek external funding sources. One source we have used to finance such purchases is vendor finance. This way, we repay in monthly or quarterly installments. For example, we’ve been working on implementing new software for the business, and the developer was kind enough to work with us by spreading the payment terms over a one-year period. So, we are using our cash flow to service the debt commitment.

P3 identified the Floor Plan as a specific source of funding:

The Floor Plan is like a loan company that provides funds to car dealers. The dealers can access the required capital for purchasing vehicles at an auction or other market. For example, the loan company made available funds up to \$300,000 for the purchase of inventory. However, another company under a different Floor Plan provided an additional \$100,000. So, with the Floor Plans, we are able to bid for vehicles at the auction and put the purchases on either Floor Plan.

Subtheme 5: Contribution Schemes

One participant reported engaging in contribution schemes with colleagues. P1 stated, “I’m involved in several monthly contribution schemes with colleagues. We take turns collecting the lump-sum cash contributed each month.” The contribution scheme provided P1 with ongoing access to capital to purchase high-cost equipment.

Document Support

Small business owners need a fundamental understanding of their organization’s financial health. As shown in D1, one way to remain informed and track operational costs and profits is to create annual financial reports. By maintaining accurate financial records, small business owners could identify the availability of internal financing to sustain operations.

Connecting Theme 2 to the Literature and Conceptual Framework

The participants reported using types of nontraditional funding before accessing external sources, including personal funds, personal borrowing, family and

spousal savings, franchising and payment plans, and contribution schemes. Theme 2 aligned with Smith (2018), who reviewed documents and interviewed six business owners about their strategies to obtain working capital and maintain operations. Like this study’s eight small business owners, Smith’s participants preferred personal funds and credit. The findings of both studies support the pecking order theory and business owners’ preference for internal funding.

According to the pecking order theory (Myers & Majluf, 1984), retained earnings, debt, and new equity are the primary business funding sources. Retained earnings are the least expensive and most preferred source of financing. In line with the pecking order theory, this study’s participants preferred nontraditional financing, commonly in personal funds or borrowing.

Theme 3: External Funding Not Readily Accessible in Earlier Years

The third theme from the interview data was that external funding was not readily accessible in the early years of the business. The small business owners found accessing loans and external funds challenging and sometimes impossible. External sources of capital are limited for small companies, and funding, when available, could be cost-prohibitive. Small business owners may use bootstrapping instead of external financing to meet their resource needs without taking on long-term debt or new equity (Winborg & Landström, 2001).

Some participants were uninterested and skeptical of loans; others tried to obtain loans but could not. P2 stated, “I actually tried to get a loan but was unsuccessful. So, I mostly used family money during my first year of operations.” Often, a new business’s credit score is insufficient to access capital. P2 shared a letter from a bank detailing a lack of credit history as the primary reason for denial. The participants interested in SBA loans said the application questions were cumbersome, and they could not handle the process at the time. The bank rates for new businesses were also unfavorable, which dissuaded participants from accessing the funds. As capital and sales rise, debt falls, except when interest rates are low (Reid, 2003).

Only two participants had obtained bank loans within the first 5 years of operation. The small business owners found that the likelihood of obtaining a loan with a favorable interest rate increased with the business’s years of existence. P6 stated,

Following the first few years of operations, it became easier to access bank loans with more favorable interest rates, terms, and conditions. We have learned that obtaining bank loans in the first few years was more difficult than it was in the later years, especially if seeking favorable interest rates.

P7 explained, “After the first 3 years, I was able to get a loan from the bank. Though it was not much ... it helped me with my business.” The participant supported this statement by sharing a loan offer letter to the small business. The inability to qualify for a loan required other means of financing for business continuity.

Document Support

The three documents—financial statements, investment performance, and financial portfolios—supported the need to develop a small business’s financial foundation and standing, and two—D1 (financial statements) and D3 (financial portfolios)—aligned with the participants’ responses and supported the subthemes. All participating small business owners had financial statements (D1), indicating they recognized the need to maintain accurate and complete financial records for their organizations’ viability and longevity. Financial statements can help business owners identify areas of improvement and make operational decisions, such as pursuing external funding and qualifying for bank loans. Financial portfolios (D3) provide insights into effective management and decision-making. Small business owners with comprehensive financial portfolio documents will likely have greater success obtaining external funding and loans with favorable terms. The financial portfolios showed that the participants had taken steps to identify potential risks and opportunities for improvement to ensure compliance with regulatory requirements and industry standards. Establishing a solid financial foundation includes investing the business profits wisely.

Connecting Theme 3 to the Literature and Conceptual Framework

The third theme showed small business owners’ difficulties obtaining financing, a finding that aligned with the pecking order theory. The participants’ experiences aligned with Greene (2020), who found that obtaining debt financing in the early stages of small business operations may be challenging because the owner is unlikely to have underlying assets to serve as collateral. In this study, P1 and P2 reported an inability to obtain external funds through loans in the early years of their businesses.

Theme 2 supported the literature on small business owners’ struggles to obtain external financing. Bank lenders often require financial statements and information to evaluate loan applications. As Aladejebi and Oladimeji (2019) indicated, maintaining these records may be difficult for SME owners. This study’s participants reported difficulties accessing external funding at the start of operations. This finding aligned with R. Brown et al. (2022), Huang et al. (2020), and Roy and Shaw (2021), who attributed the lack of access to limited credit history, incomplete record-keeping, and insufficient collateral.

Theme 4: External Financing Used at Later and Critical Stages of Business

The participants commonly relied on internal financing in the earlier stages of their businesses. Most small business owners reported using external financing after the first 5 years of operation. Only P6 and P7 used external financing options such as bank loans in the first 5

years. P2 believed starting a business with personal funds was better to ensure its profitability, noting that launching a business was risky and that an entrepreneur should know how to trade with personal funds before seeking external loans. Table 3 shows the emergent subthemes within Theme 4.

Table 3

Theme 4: External Financing Used at Later and Critical Stages of Business – Subthemes

Subthemes	<i>n</i> participants referencing the theme	<i>n</i> times referenced
1. External financing often used at critical stages of business	6	21
2. Careful consideration of external debt before use	5	2
3. Use of new equity	5	7
4. Other sources of external financing	2	5

Note. *N* = 8.

Subtheme 1: External Financing Often Used at Critical Stages of Business

In addition to using external funding in later years, the small business owners also reported pursuing outside funds to survive difficult times. P3 reported obtaining external funding after the first 5 years of operation:

We used external funding in my business to sustain operations during a very difficult period. At a time when we had nowhere to turn or had no hope of survival, external funding really helped us sustain our operations and keep our doors open for business. External funding may sometimes be expensive, but that is the cost of keeping the business open.

The participants considered external financing options when their businesses did not generate sufficient revenue for profitable operations. P5 reported that when her business had a positive cash flow, she used the profits earned for operation. However, the COVID-19 pandemic had reduced the business’s profitability, and she planned to take out a loan. P5 explained,

The use of bank loans would be at a period when we are not profitable, which is the situation right now. When the business is profitable, we reinvest our funds, and this is when we purchase new equipment. We purchase a new piece of equipment every year.

None of the eight participants interviewed reported using external financing to start their businesses or fund early operations. As shown in Theme 1, internal funding was the preferred way to obtain operational funds. Among the participants who had acquired external financing, they did so only after considering their options and later in their businesses’ operation.

Subtheme 2: Careful Consideration of External Debt Before Use

The participants reported exhausting their internal funds before examining the external financing option. Most small business owners in this study felt that although external financing could benefit the business, its pursuit required careful and thoughtful consideration. When external funding was necessary, the least expensive source was preferable. P2 stated,

I utilize external debt according to the associated cost of the funds. I utilize the loans with lower associated costs before the ones that have higher costs. However, I try not to draw down on the loans I consider to be expensive.

P4 and P7 considered all available sources’ interest rates before making a selection. P7 had access to bank loans, SBA loans, and credit with varying interest rates. The participant explained, “I first consider what kind of operations I need the funds for. If it’s a long-term opportunity, I go with the lowest interest rate for. If it’s a short-term business opportunity, I’ll take what I can get.” P4 stated that loan providers’ interest rates must be reasonable for her to take a loan. Most business owners recommended avoiding high-interest loans. Low interest rates and extended repayment periods emerged as preferences for securing external funding sources. P4 shared, “I received several loan offers and credit card approval letters I did not use due to unfavorable terms.” The loan interest rate had a significant impact on its value and attractiveness. Even with an extended repayment plan, P7 said, “It’s always better to pay the loan off within a year.”

In addition to the interest rate, the terms and conditions attached to the loans were considerations. P7 stated,

It is important to note the terms and conditions written in loan documents, and a borrower needs to be very careful, as there are lots of details in the

fine print. Not paying attention to these terms and conditions can be very costly if issues arise in the future.

P7 recommended “avoiding predatory lenders that don’t give you all the lending conditions until after the loan’s signed.” The participants recommended understanding financial capital and seeking professional advice when taking out loans.

Participants suggested obtaining external funding to improve and expand the business, not to operate the business or pay bills. P5 stated, “We’ve used loans to fund improvements in our business but not [to] finance regular business operations.” The participant believed that any business owner needing loans to pay operational bills or sustain operations should close the organization, as it is unsuccessful. Although expansion may be beneficial, most participants recommended small business owners avoid incurring significant debt to the business’s detriment. P7 found that “taking on loans and debt when you’re trying to expand could end up hurting your business, especially if you use company income to pay back the debt.” External financing also comes with the risk of repayment defaults. P2 reported “avoiding outside loans or credit as much as possible.”

Unlike the heads of larger, more established companies, small business owners face severe disadvantages while seeking financing (Hossain, 2013). Although bank lending was uncommon among the sample, P6 and P7 reported acquiring loans to support their businesses during the first 5 years of operations. Both participants noted the positive impact on their businesses and their ability to repay the loans. P6 stated, “To fund our business, we’ve maintained a 60/40 split between bank debt and internal cash.” The participant continued, “The equipment was expensive, and we didn’t have enough internally generated cash to buy it.” P6 used bank loans with favorable terms and low interest rates to acquire the equipment needed for business operations. P7 reported receiving loan approval after 3 years of maintaining business records. P7 said, “The only problem with bank loans is when a business owner cannot repay the funds.”

Subtheme 3: Use of New Equity

Raising new equity was unattractive to most small business owners in the early stages. One participant had used new equity as a source of funding. Although equity providers had approached two participants, the business owners were skeptical. P1, a clinical services provider, believed the private equity company would be too profit-focused, affecting the quality of his business’s services and goodwill to clients. The participant said,

We are currently negotiating [a] potential equity investment from a company now, but I am not sure we will accept their investment offer. This is because we have concerns as to the quality of care

that will be provided by these investors should they assume ownership of the company.

P1 supported his statement with a screenshare of an email from the prospective investors regarding their interest in acquiring a controlling stake in the clinic.

P3 used new equity to sustain the business at a difficult time, staying open because of the new equity plan. P3 stated,

New investors have really helped the business, especially in difficult times. Even though their support tends to be expensive, they keep the business open. Had it not been for new equity and debt, the business would have been closed due to a lack of inventory. The only asset the company would then have is the building, and that would have gone into foreclosure without any earnings.

Five participants discussed the option of private equity, and most reported choosing not to engage with a private equity firm. P4 said, “Early on, when I realized I needed more than my original investment to keep the business going, I looked into hiring a private equity firm. I wasn’t willing to give up a share in my company’s success.” P5 stated, “If there are going to be stakeholders in the business, I’m going to decide who they are.” P8 expressed similar sentiments, saying, “I’d rather let my Uncle Bob invest and get a portion of the profits than hire a private equity firm. And I don’t like my Uncle Bob very much.” The participants voiced concerns about the cost of financing regarding reduced profits, less control of operations, and threats to their customer service and organizational mission.

Subtheme 4: Other Sources of External Financing

The study participants discussed several additional external financing sources, including third-party debt funding, SBA loans, government grants, and moneylenders. Few participants had access to or used external funding sources. P7 could access and preferred to use multiple external funds as he did not want to “put all his eggs in one basket.” He reported engaging with different financial institutions to “spread things around” and sustain his business. P7 shared two loan approval documents and pointed out the differences in some terms and conditions. His ability to choose between the providers allowed him greater access to funds.

Two participants reported accessing SBA loans. P7 stated, “I have found the SBA loan quite beneficial to keeping my business on track. The terms can’t be beat.” P8 said,

When it came time to secure more money to grow my business, I researched all sorts of external options: bank loans, private lenders, and SBA loans. SBA was the best option, hands down. They had the lowest interest rates without requiring property as collateral.

“Strategies to Obtain Working Capital for Small Businesses”

The SBA provides subsidized loans with favorable terms to help small businesses grow. Unlike loan officers at the big banks who would not lend to him, the SBA lenders provided loans that allowed P7 to run his business. He remarked,

I was able to get in on the SBA train. The best thing for any small business is to engage with the SBA to access subsidized loans. I don’t know what is happening in America regarding loans, but SBA is still the best source for loans.

Two small business owners reported different means of acquiring external funds. One participant (P1) had received a government grant to provide services to the local county jail. P3 was the only small business owner to report borrowing from a moneylender, obtaining a lower interest rate than the banks but with a shorter repayment period.

Document Support

D1, D2, and D3 supported Theme 3. Small businesses’ financial records provide insights into the effectiveness of daily management and decision-making. These documents indicate potential risks and opportunities for improvement, ensure compliance with regulatory requirements and industry standards, and enable small business owners to make business financing decisions.

Connecting Theme 4 to the Literature and Conceptual Framework

The fourth theme addressed the lack of external financing used by small business owners, especially during the early stages of operation. This finding suggests that the pecking order theory may apply to small businesses but not at all stages. In line with the pecking order theory’s hierarchy of financing sources—retained earnings, debt, and new equity (Myers & Majluf, 1984)—the participants turned to external funding sources when no internal options existed. Despite the logic of the pecking order theory, internal financing might be unavailable to the owners of small businesses and new entities.

Berger and Udell (1998) found that different capital structures are appropriate at various points in the business life cycle. P3 discussed the need to obtain external funding after 5 years of operation when the business was at risk of closure. P5 also relied on bank loans during nonprofitable

times, one of which occurred during the interview. Two participants, P6 and P7, had obtained bank loans after operating for 5 and 3 years, respectively.

Given the high failure rate of small businesses and the associated level of risk, bank lenders have had to reallocate credit from riskier markets to safer ones (Cortés et al., 2020). This shift has led to decreased external debt available to small business owners and their subsequent preference for internal funding. The participants urged caution when considering external funding sources. One participant recalled a lender who seemed to be predatory and trying to take advantage of him. P1 was reluctant to consider equity participation from a larger company due to concerns about losing control and focusing too much on profit and too little on client services. New equity providers receive some control over the operations of the businesses in which they invest (Dowling et al., 2019). Internal funds are the only source guaranteeing that the small business owner retains complete business control.

Theme 4 supported the literature on small business owners’ use of external financing at later or critical stages. In Ahmed’s (2019) study, owners reported not pursuing external financing until they had improved their credit history and financial literacy, demonstrating creditworthiness to banks and other lenders. Thorgren and Williams (2020) found that an expected crisis (COVID-19) drove SME leaders to pursue external financing or government support to avoid closure during this uniquely devastating event.

Theme 5: Minimizing Business Operational Costs and Expenses

The final emergent theme from data analysis was the owners’ business management in a manner that reduced operational costs. As shown in prior themes, internal funding was the most frequently used source, and external financing was not readily accessible in the first 5 years of business operations. A financial strategy adopted by five of the eight participants was operating and managing their businesses to minimize expenditures. The five small business owners under this theme did not have access to bank loans in the first 5 years of business operations. Table 4 shows the emergent subthemes within Theme 5.

Table 4
Theme 5: Minimizing Business Operational Costs and Expenses – Subthemes

Subthemes	<i>n</i> participants referencing the theme	<i>n</i> times referenced
1. Minimizing business expenses	4	13
2. Not paying self	3	4
3. Leveraging relationships	2	2
4. Giving company shares to employees as payment	1	3

Note. *N* = 8.

Subtheme 1: Minimizing Business Expenses

Four small business owners discussed minimizing expenses by reducing the number of employees, overworking, and taking on multiple roles to reduce payroll costs. P1 explained,

Business owners use various strategies to minimize their business expenses. So, the main thing for us is to ensure we didn't accumulate so much debt that would now begin to threaten our survival. And to achieve this, we kept our operational expenses to a minimum.

P2 reported overworking as the office manager, instructor, and coordinator. Hiring other workers or coordinators would have increased her expenses, so she took on the roles herself. P2 remarked, “I didn't even feel the pain of working long hours. I'll be in the office [from] about 7 in the morning until 11:30 p.m. I did that consistently throughout the year. I just spent my sweat and blood.”

P2 reported being very conservative with her office space requirements. She explained, “I don't need to impress anybody. I just need to meet the customer's needs.” The participant rejected fancy or extravagant decor, opting to keep the environment basic and clean. She mentioned that her late husband had ordered several items to beautify the office space, but she returned everything and put the money into the business. P8 reported leasing all office equipment to minimize costs and manage cash flow. P8 said, “I leased everything minus my Lexmark printer and Brother fax machine. Other than those, all my other equipment was leased.” Among the approaches the participants reported taking to keep their business expenses at a minimum, the most common was working extra hours.

Subtheme 2: Not Paying Self

The participants minimized operational costs was by reinvesting their earnings in the business. P1, P2, and P8 did not take a salary in the early years of business operations. P2 shared, “What I did in terms of raising funds was that I did not earn a salary in the first few years. I took on the role of the manager.” P8 said, “I did not pay myself at some points and took pay cuts at other times.” He had a long-term vision, so he did not take out much money as payment. P1 remarked, “We still use a lot of sweat equity. I have other sources of income, so I don't always earn a salary.” Three of this study's participants worked without pay for a time to ensure business continuity.

Subtheme 3: Leveraging Relationships

Other strategies the participants mentioned to maintain continued operations and reduce expenses included leveraging relationships and sharing office space. P2 relied on a relationship with a friend to obtain business space. She explained,

My friend allocates me a space within her office, and I pay her for that space monthly without the burden of a lease. I probably happened to be in the

right place at the right time. Also, I am surrounded by the right people.

P1 reported sharing office space with other physicians when starting his business to minimize costs. As the company progressed, he began to expand operations. These two participants benefited from professional and personal relationships. Shared office space reduced their operational costs, enabling them to sustain operations.

Subtheme 4: Giving Company Shares to Employees as Payment

P3 allowed essential and valuable employees to use part of their salaries to buy shares in the company. In this way, P3 reduced salaries by “short paying.” He mentioned his assistant manager, who had a 30% equity stake in the company. “His input was extremely valuable, and I couldn't afford to pay him what he deserved. So, I offered him 30% of the company shares,” which enabled P3 to achieve other operational goals. He stated, “Short paying was like underpaying the staff [in exchange] for a share of the company. I did this for the most valuable members of my team.”

Document Support

The three documents—financial statements (D1), investment performance (D2), and financial portfolios (D3)—provided a comprehensive understanding of a small business's finances. Small business owners could review the documents to identify ways to minimize operational costs and expenses and identify potential risks. Owners may better control small business operations by maintaining regular and accurate financial records.

Connecting Theme 5 to the Literature and Conceptual Framework

The findings for Theme 5 supported the conceptual framework of the pecking order theory, indicating a preference for funding the business internally, only turning to the use of equity when internal financing and debt were unavailable (Myers & Majluf, 1984). Three participating small business owners (P1, P2, and P8) opted not to take a salary to minimize costs. P3 allowed top employees to obtain equity in the business, granting partial ownership in place of additional salary. In this way, the employees invested a part of their wages to obtain an equity stake in the company.

External equity may be essential for unprofitable businesses with limited cash flow or a high risk of failure (Vanacker & Manigart, 2010). Although equity is the most expensive funding source, repayment is unnecessary when earnings decline (Martinez et al., 2019). In their interviews, the participants supported equity as a preferred funding source because small businesses have high failure rates and limited cashflows in the early stages of operations. This finding contrasts with the pecking order theory, which suggests equity as a last resort for funding small businesses.

Theme 5 supported the literature specific to minimizing operational costs and expenses. P1, P2, and P8’s decisions not to take a salary aligned with Thorgren and Williams’s (2020) study respondents, who reported owners and board members forgoing compensation or accepting reduced salaries. This theme also aligned with the suggestion to limit in-office expenses, such as salaries (FNCB Bank, n.d.).

Applications to Professional Practice

This qualitative descriptive multiple case study was a means to explore strategies small business owners use to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond 5 years. Eight participants took part in semistructured, one-on-one interviews. The findings may provide information for potential entrepreneurs to start sustainable small businesses and maintain operations for over 5 years. The lack of strategies to obtain working capital hinders the sustainability of some small businesses. SME owners face several constraints, including limited finances and low entrepreneurial knowledge (Nkwabi & Mboya, 2019). This study’s findings may be helpful to small business owners, providing insight into strategies to obtain working capital for sustaining operations beyond the first 5 years. As the pecking order theory suggests, small business owners typically use internally generated money or personal savings before seeking external debt or new equity (Myers & Majluf, 1984). The participants’ funding choices aligned with the pecking order theory.

Entrepreneurs seeking to start a small business may devise helpful capital-sourcing strategies from the themes that emerged in this study. Lack of financing is a critical external factor hindering small businesses’ sustainability (Fatoki, 2014b). Entrepreneurs may apply the strategies this study’s participants discussed to ensure their small businesses are sustainable and operational beyond 5 years. Likewise, business leaders could use this information to devise financial strategies to prepare themselves for some funding challenges facing entrepreneurs starting a new business.

Implications for Social Change

Small businesses are an essential part of an economy’s ecosystem. The U.S. SBA (2020a) noted that small businesses are critical to a growing economy. The importance of small businesses is multidimensional, as owners provide jobs in communities where they operate and pay taxes to the local government. The information provided in this study could contribute to small business owners’ knowledge of funding strategies to adopt for sustaining business operations beyond the first 5 years. The implications for social change are that small business owners may sustain operations for more than 5 years, providing jobs and tax revenue to citizens and communities.

Entrepreneurs are essential to job creation and economic development (Allen & Curington, 2014). Small

businesses’ failure rate in the first 5 years of operations is 50%, and such organizations account for about 41% of private payroll in the United States (Turner & Endres, 2017). Several authors have noted small businesses’ social impact and contributions. Applying the five themes that emerged in this study could impact a small business’s success. Small business sustainability has a significant social impact on the local economy and citizens’ livelihoods.

Recommendations for Action

A small business’s long-term survivability extends from sustainability beyond the first 5 years. Given the high failure rate of small businesses, entrepreneurs must increase their financial knowledge and strategic understanding of funding operations. One recommendation is for entrepreneurs to use internal financing to sustain operations, as this study’s participants often did, minimizing the need for external funds. Small business owners could consider using personal funds, including savings, home equity, investments, outside salaries, and personal loans.

Based on this study’s findings, another recommendation is to invest the business’s profit into expanding and sustaining operations. Some entrepreneurs may explore franchising, which provides inventory and low-cost equipment leasing. Collaborating with other businesses to purchase and share equipment could reduce the amount borrowed.

Small business owners should use lower-cost sources of funds for as long as possible before pursuing external financing. Although often necessary at critical operating stages, external debt requires informed and thoughtful consideration. Small business owners must review and understand funding terms and conditions and examine interest rates across sources, including bank and SBA loans.

Small business owners can increase their likelihood of success by maintaining high personal credit scores and clean credit histories. Additional recommendations are for small business owners to maintain comprehensive records, including annual financial statements, and develop the business’s credit history and score to better their chances of obtaining bank and other external financing.

As shown in Theme 4, small business owners should minimize business expenses to reduce operational costs and ensure sustainability beyond 5 years. Careful consideration should precede any equipment purchase to determine whether the item is necessary and, if so, whether there are less expensive means of acquisition. One way to reduce costs is by leveraging relationships. P8 leased all office equipment to maintain cash flow, and P1 and P2 leveraged relationships to obtain a site for their businesses.

Government leaders must understand the growth stages of small businesses and entrepreneurs’ issues in order to design good policies (Gobble, 2016). Improved comprehension could lead to a better ecosystem that can

support small business owners and improve their chances of survival beyond the first 5 years. Informed legislative actions would facilitate a better ecosystem supporting entrepreneurs and improving their survival chances beyond the first 5 years.

Recommendations for Further Research

Future researchers could repeat this study but increase the number of participants and expand the geographical range. Because this study was qualitative, the collected data included no numbers or variables. A quantitative approach could show the correlation between variables, such as business type, credit history, and internal and external financing. A mixed methods study would benefit from a qualitative participant perspective and quantitative data.

This study involved eight participants from diverse industries and sectors, and the sample size and composition were appropriate to obtain different entrepreneur experiences. Future researchers may want to adopt a narrower scope centered on the perspectives of successful small business owners in a single sector or industry. Focused studies could be helpful for industry professionals and organizations.

This qualitative study focused on the owners of successful small businesses in Maryland. Future research should conduct a similar study in other states, cities, or countries. Using participants across a broader geographical range could improve reliability and validity.

Reflections

When I enrolled in the DBA program, I expected the journey to be uncomplicated but challenging. The program afforded me the privilege of meeting and discussing with classmates and faculty and inspiring small business owners. As I began to develop the criteria for participation, I found the initial selection of small business owners challenging. I narrowed the list and identified eight qualified small business owners interested in participating in the study. I selected a qualitative approach, which I believed would be more straightforward than quantitative methods. I quickly realized the rigor of data collection and analysis and the depth of insight gained from a qualitative study. Although I initially overestimated the number of weekly submissions, I eventually got better at preparing for and understanding the process.

With a master’s degree in business, I had previous exposure to business theories and expected to complete the dissertation without difficulty. I was unprepared for the precision and processes involved in conducting academic research. Throughout the dissertation, I learned how to conduct interviews, gather and analyze data, and ensure a study’s credibility and validity.

A realistic term plan with identified stretch targets was a good motivator. After completing this study, I am conversant with academic research processes and can

transfer these skills across different study areas. I learned the importance of peer reviews and why they are necessary. Finally, I broadened my understanding of operating and sustaining small businesses through interviews with eight participants, where I learned from their experiences. My doctoral journey has been invaluable, and I will continue to embrace the spirit of learning by researching and writing articles in the field of business.

CONCLUSION

Small businesses play an essential role in economic development (Ayandibu & Houghton, 2017; Dar et al., 2017; Mills, 2018; Ribeiro-Soriano, 2017), and their high failure rates negatively impact the economy. This qualitative descriptive multiple case study explored small business owners’ strategies to obtain working capital for business continuity beyond 5 years. The study focused on how small business owners accessed financing to sustain operations. The five themes from participant interviews represented strategies the successful small business owners used to obtain funding.

The leaders of large corporations and small businesses need to raise adequate capital, but the latter’s task is often more arduous. This challenge underscores the importance of understanding financial strategies when starting and operating a small business. Using the right funding strategy could significantly impact a business’s profitability, success, or failure. This study’s findings aligned with the literature and the theoretical framework.

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“Strategies to Obtain Working Capital for Small Businesses”

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Appendix A: Interview Protocol

Interview protocol	
What you will do	What you will say—script
Introduce the interview and set the stage—often over a meal or coffee	Thank you for taking time out of your schedule to meet with me today; I know you are very busy. I have scheduled our interview for 1 hour; however, it may take less time depending on the extent of our discussion. I have seven prepared questions for you, all of which will allow you to provide answers in as much depth as you like. I may also ask follow-up questions to explore further some of your experiences or perspectives. If at any time you become uncomfortable with a question or topic or wish to take a break, please just let me know. Do you have any questions before we begin? Great. I will now start the audio recorder.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Watch for nonverbal cues • Paraphrase as needed • Ask follow-up probing questions to get more in-depth 	• What strategies did you use in obtaining working capital?
	• What are potential sources of working capital?
	• What are the significant challenges you encountered in securing working capital?
	• How did you overcome the challenges you encountered in securing working capital?
	• What strategies did you use in developing successful banking relationships to secure working capital?
	• Based on your experience, how have external funding or new equity affected your business sustainability and profitability?
	• What else can you share about the funding strategies you used for the sustainability of your business during the first 5 years of your operation?
What you will do	What you will say—script
Schedule follow-up member checking interview	I anticipate analyzing all data and identifying preliminary themes within 3 to 4 weeks. Can we schedule some time next month so you can review my findings and provide your informed opinions and feedback?
Follow-Up Member Checking Interview Protocol	
What you will do	What you will say—script

“Strategies to Obtain Working Capital for Small Businesses”

Introduce the interview and set the stage	Thank you again for the generous allowance of your time for this process. I will again audio record our conversation to ensure I do not miss anything. Do you have any questions before we begin? Great; let’s get started.
Share a copy of the succinct synthesis for each individual question	Script XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
Bring in probing questions related to other information that you may have found—note the information must be related so that you are probing and adhering to the IRB approval. Walk through each question, read the interpretation, and ask: Did I miss anything? Or, What would you like to add?	• What strategies did you use in obtaining working capital? Transcribed Interview Response.
	• What are potential sources of working capital? Transcribed Interview Response.
	• What are the significant challenges you encountered in securing working capital? Transcribed Interview Response.
	• How did you overcome the challenges you encountered in securing working capital? Transcribed Interview Response.
	• What strategies did you use in developing successful banking relationships to secure working capital? Transcribed Interview Response.
	• How, if at all, did you have to modify the initial strategies you used for obtaining working capital? Transcribed Interview Response.
What you will do	What you will say—script
	• What else can you share about the funding strategies you used for the sustainability of your business during the first 5 years of your operation? Transcribed Interview Response.

Appendix B: IRB Partner Organization Agreement

Insert:

Partner Organization Name

Partner Organization Email Address

Partner Organization Phone Number

Date

The doctoral student, Soloman Atamaya is conducting a case study involving our organization and is therefore approved to collect interview data from one or more of our organization’s leaders (managers, directors, or decision-makers whom I will identify to the student).

INTERNAL RECORDS (OPTIONAL):

The signer of this agreement should indicate which internal documents, if any, can be shared with the researcher.

- Our organization cannot allow access to internal records.
- Our organization will allow this student to analyze the following internal records that I deem appropriate (*and shall be de-identified or redacted, as needed*):
 - training materials*
 - protocols*
 - manuals*
 - reports*
 - agreements*
 - operational records*
 - meeting minutes*

“Strategies to Obtain Working Capital for Small Businesses”

digital/audio/video documents

other internal documents: _____

STUDENT RESPONSIBILITIES

I understand that, as per the student doctoral program requirements, the student will publish a scholarly report of this case study project in ProQuest as a doctoral capstone (withholding the names of the organization and participating individuals), as per the following ethical standards:

- In all reports (including drafts shared with peers and faculty members), the student is required to maintain confidentiality by removing names and key pieces of evidence/data that might disclose an organization’s/individual’s identity or inappropriately divulge proprietary details. If the organization itself wishes to publicize the findings of this project, that is the organization’s judgment call. `
- The student will be responsible for complying with the organization’s policies and requirements regarding data collection (including the need for the partner organization’s internal ethics/regulatory approval, if applicable).
- Via an Interview Consent Form, the student will describe to interviewees how the data will be used in the doctoral project and how all interviewees’ privacy will be protected.
- The doctoral student will not use these data for any purpose other than the doctoral study outlined in this agreement.

I confirm that I am authorized to approve research activities in this setting.

Signature _____

Partner Organization Leader’s Name and Title _____